

**Taxonomic and chemical survey of ascomycetes associated with the
production of cytochalasans and examining their influence on
actin filament remodeling**

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Vorveröffentlichungen der Dissertation

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List of publications

Sole or shared first-authorships are underlined, cases of co/correspondence are marked with an asterisk, and equal contributions of the author are highlighted with ¹.

- I. Pourmoghaddham MJ, **Lambert C**, Surup F, Khodaparast SA, Krisai-Greilhuber I, Voglmayr H, Stadler M. **2020**. Discovery of a new species of the *Hypoxylon rubiginosum* complex from Iran and antagonistic activities of *Hypoxylon* spp. against the Ash Dieback pathogen, *Hymenoscyphus fraxineus*, in dual culture. *Myckeys* 66:105-133. Doi: 10.3897/MYCOKEYS.66.50946.
- II. Stadler M, **Lambert C**, Wibberg D, Kalinowski J, Cox RJ, Kolařík M, Kuhnert E. **2020**. Intragenomic polymorphisms in the ITS region of high-quality genomes of the Hypoxylaceae (Xylariales, Ascomycota). *Mycol Prog* 19:235-245. Doi: 10.1007/s11557-019-01552-9.
- III. Samarakoon MC, Thongbai B, Hyde KD, Brönstrup M, Beutling U, **Lambert C**, Miller AN, Liu JKJ, Promputtha I, Stadler M. **2020**. Elucidation of the life cycle of the endophytic genus *Muscodor* and its transfer to *Induratia* in Induratiaceae fam. nov., based on a polyphasic taxonomic approach. *Fungal Divers* 101(1):177-210. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13225-020-00443-9>.
- IV. Moussa AY, **Lambert C**, Stradal TEB, Ashrafi S, Maier W, Stadler M, Helaly SE. **2020**. New peptaibiotics and a cyclodepsipeptide from *Ijuhya vitellina*: Isolation, identification, cytotoxic and nematicidal activities. *Antibiotics*, 9(3):1-13. Doi: 10.3390/antibiotics9030132.
- V. Wittstein K, Cordsmeier A, **Lambert C**, Wendt L, Sir EB, Wurzler N, Petrini LE, Stadler M. **2020**. Identification of *Rosellinia* species as producers of cyclodepsipeptide PF1022 A and resurrection of the genus *Dematophora* as

- inferred from polythetic taxonomy. *Stud Mycol* 96, 1-16. Doi: 10.1016/j.simyco.2020.01.001.
- VI. Becker K, **Lambert C**, Wieschhaus J, Stadler M. **2020**. Phylogenetic assignment of the fungicolous *Hypoxylon invadens* (Ascomycota, Xylariales) and investigation of its secondary metabolites. *Microorganisms* 8(9):1-14. Doi: 10.3390/microorganisms8091397.
- VII. Wang C, **Lambert C**, Hauser M, Deuschmann A, Zeilinger C, Rottner K, Stradal TEB, Stadler M, Skellam EJ, Cox RJ. **2020**. Diversely functionalised cytochalasins through mutasynthesis and semi-synthesis. *Chem Eur J* 26(60):13578-13583. Doi: 10.1002/chem.202002241.
- VIII. Wibberg D, Stadler M, **Lambert C**, Bunk B, Spröer C, Rückert C, Kalinowski J, Cox RJ, Kuhnert E. **2021**. High quality genome sequences of thirteen Hypoxylaceae (Ascomycota) strengthen the phylogenetic family backbone and enable the discovery of new taxa. *Fungal Divers*, 106(1):7-28. Doi: 10.1007/s13225-020-00447-5.
- IX. **Lambert C**¹, Pourmoghaddham MJ¹, Cedeño-Sanchez M, Surup F, Khodaparast SA, Krisai-Greilhuber I, Voglmayr H, Stradal TEB, Stadler M. **2021**. Resolution of the *Hypoxylon fuscum* complex (Hypoxylaceae, Xylariales) and discovery and biological characterization of two of its prominent secondary metabolites. *Journal of Fungi* 7(2):131. Doi: 10.3390/jof7020131.
- X. Matio Kemuignou B, Schweizer L, **Lambert C**, Anoumedem EGM, Kouam SF, Stadler M, Marin-Felix Y. **2022**. New polyketides from the liquid culture of *Diaporthe breyniae* sp. nov. (Diaporthales, Diaporthaceae). *MycKeys* 90: 85–118. Doi: 10.3897/mycokeys.90.82871.
- XI. Garcia KYM, Quimque MTJ, **Lambert C**, Schmidt K, Primahana G, Stradal TEB, Ratzenböck A, Dahse HM, Phukhamsakda C, Stadler M, Surup F, Macabeo APG. **2022**. Antiproliferative and Cytotoxic Cytochalasins from *Sparticola triseptata* Inhibit Actin Polymerization and Aggregation. *Journal of Fungi* 5(6):560. Doi: 10.3390/jof8060560.
- XII. Pourmoghaddham MJ, **Lambert C**, Voglmayr H, Khodaparast SA, Krisai-Greilhuber I, Stadler M. **2022**. Note on the genus *Nemania* (Xylariaceae)—first records and a new species of the genus from Iran. *MycKeys* 93:81-105. Doi: 10.3897/mycokeys.93.94148.

- XIII. Pourmoghaddham MJ, Ekiz G, **Lambert C**, Surup F, Primahana G, Wittstein K, Khodaparast SA, Voglmayr H, Krisai-Greilhuber I, Stradal TEB, Stadler M. **2022**. Studies on the secondary metabolism of *Rosellinia* and *Dematophora* strains (Xylariaceae) from Iran. *Mycol Prog* 21(8):65. Doi: 10.1007/s11557-022-01816-x.
- XIV. **Lambert C**, Schweizer L, Kemkuignou BM, Anoumedem EGM, Kouam SF, Marin-Felix Y. **2023**. Four new endophytic species of *Diaporthe* (Diaporthaceae, Diaporthales) isolated from Cameroon. *Myckeys* 23(99):319-362. Doi: 10.3897/myckeys.99.110043.
- XV. Cedeño-Sánchez M, Charria-Girón E, **Lambert C**, Luangsa-ard JJ, Decock C, Franke R, Brönstrup M, Stadler M. **2023**. Segregation of the genus *Parahyoxylon* (Hypoxylaceae, Xylariales) from *Hyoxylon* by a polyphasic taxonomic approach. *Myckeys* 95:131-162. Doi: 10.3897/myckeys.95.98125.
- XVI. Matio Kemkuignou B, **Lambert C**, Schmidt K, Schweizer L, Anoumedem EGM, Kouam SF, Stadler M, Stradal T, Marin-Felix Y. **2023**. Unreported cytochalasins from an acid-mediated transformation of cytochalasin J isolated from *Diaporthe* cf. *ueckeri*. *Fitoterapia* 166:105434. Doi: 10.1016/j.fitote.2023.105434.
- XVII. **Lambert C**, Schiefelbein R, Jaimez JA, Stadler M, Sir EB. **2023**. Studies on Argentine *Phylacia* species (Hypoxylaceae) using a polythetic taxonomic approach. *Mycol Prog* 22(4):27. Doi: 10.1007/s11557-023-01875-8.
- XVIII. **Lambert C**, Shao L, Zeng H, Surup F, Saetang P, Aime MC, Husbands DR, Rottner K, Stradal TEB, Stadler M. **2023**. Cytochalasins produced by *Xylaria karyophthora* and their biological activities. *Mycologia* 115(3):277-287. Doi: 10.1080/00275514.2023.2188868.
- XIX. Niego AGT, **Lambert C**, Mortimer P, THongklang N, Rapior S, Grosse M, Schrey H, Charria-Girón E, Walker A, Hyde KD, Stadler M. **2023**. The contribution of fungi to the global economy. *Fungal Divers* 121(1):95-137. Doi: 10.1007/s13225-023-00520-9.
- XX. Kemkuignou Matio B, **Lambert C**, Stadler M, Fogue SK, Marin-Felix Y. **2023**. Unprecedented antimicrobial and cytotoxic polyketides from cultures of *Diaporthe africana* sp. nov. *J Fungi* 9(7):781. Doi: 10.3390/jof9070781.

- XXI. **Lambert C***, Schmidt K, Karger M, Stadler M, Stradal TEB, Rottner K*. **2023**. Cytochalasins and Their Impact on Actin Filament Remodeling. *Biomolecules* 13(8):1247. Doi: 10.3390/biom13081247.
- XXII. Cedeño-Sanchez M, Schiefelbein R, Stadler M, Voglmayr H, Bensch K, **Lambert C***. **2023**. Redisposition of apiosporous genera *Induratia* and *Muscodor* in the Xylariales, following the discovery of an authentic strain of *Induratia apiospora*. *Botanical Studies* 64(1):1-17. Doi: 10.1186/s40529-023-00372-1.
- XXIII. Cedeño-Sanchez M, Cheng T, **Lambert C**, Kolařík M, Kuhnert E, Cox RJ, Kalinowski J, Verwaaijen B, Stadler M. **2024**. Unraveling intragenomic polymorphisms in the high-quality genome of Hypoxylaceae: a comprehensive study of the rDNA cistron. *Mycol Prog* 23:5. Doi: 10.1007/s11557-023-01940-2.
- XXIV. **Lambert C**, Karger M, Steffen A, Tang Y, Döring , Stradal TEB, Lappalainen P, Faix J, Bieling P, Rottner K. **2024**. Differential interference with actin binding protein function by acute Cytochalasin B. *Curr Biol*, in submission.

Tagungsbeiträge

Lambert C, Shao L, Ekiz G, Pourmoghaddam MJ, Aime MC, Surup F, Khodaparast SA, Krisai-Greilhuber I, Voglmayr H, Stradal TEB, Stadler M. Progress on the structure activity relationship of cytochalasins isolated from Xylariaceae impairing eukaryotic actin cytoskeletal organization by tracking changes in bioactivity. 100th Anniversary of the German Mycological Society (DGfM), Blaubeuren, Germany, 04.-07.10.2021.

Wang C, **Lambert C**, Kishore A, Zeilinger C, Rottner K, Stradal TEB, Stadler M, Skellam EJ and Cox RC. Semi-synthetic functionalization and manipulation of the eukaryotic actin cytoskeleton by cytochalasins. 4th European Conference on Natural Products, Virtual Conference hosted by DeCheMa, 06-08.09.2021.

Lambert C, Steffen A, Karger M, Stadler M, Lappalainen P, Stradal TEB, Rottner K. Capping protein is required for the cytochalasin B-induced accumulation of VASP at the lamellipodium tip. Actin Assembly for Intracellular Functions, Freiburg, Germany, 10.-12.05.2023.

Lambert C. Polyphasic taxonomic characterization of selected Xylariales (Ascomycota) and their potential as new sources of bioactive secondary metabolites. XI Congreso Latinoamericano De Micología, Panama, Panama, 07.08.-10.08.2023.

Lambert C. Examining acute cytochalasan effects on lamellipodial actin regulators using local application. XI Congreso Latinoamericano De Micología, Panama, Panama, 07.08.-10.08.2023.

Posterbeiträge

Lambert C, Shao L, Ekiz G, Pourmoghaddam MJ, Aime MC, Surup F, Khodaparast SA, Krisai-Greilhuber I, Voglmayr H, Stradal TEB, Stadler M. Characterization of cytochalasins isolated from Xylariaceae and description of their bioactivity on the eukaryotic actin cytoskeleton. RISE of the Fungi Symposium, Utrecht, Netherlands, 21.-22.04.2022.

Lambert C, Steffen A, Karger M, Stradal TEB, Stadler M, Rottner K. Manipulation of kinetics and turnover of lamellipodial actin regulators by local cytochalasan administration. European Cytoskeleton Forum, Hannover, Germany, 16.-19.05.2022.

Lambert C, Steffen A, Karger M, Stadler M, Lappalainen P, Stradal TEB, Rottner K. Examining acute cytochalasan effects on lamellipodial actin regulators using local application. Helmholtz-Centre for Pharmaceutical Research (HIPS) Symposium, Saarbrücken, Germany, 04.05.2023.

Declaration of contribution to publications

The contribution of Christopher Lambert (CL) and the co-authors to the papers listed above are as follows:

- I. MJP collected, isolated and morphologically characterized surveyed specimens. CL sequenced the strains. MJP and CL inferred phylogenies. Stroma material was extracted and put into chemotaxonomic context by CL. Additional specimens to screen for *Hymenoscyphus fraxineus* antagonism were mutually agreed upon by MJP, CL and MS. MJP screened the specimens against *H. fraxineus* and CL helped with dereplication and chemical analysis. FS supervised the analytical chemistry, KSA, IKG and HV supervised morphological and phylogenetic characterization. MJP and CL drafted the manuscript; all authors reviewed and edited the draft until finalization by MS. Both KSA and MS supervised the entire project.
- II. MS conceptualized the study, CL extracted sequences from genomes of Hypoxylaceae and added a mock – molecular phylogenetic inference of the ITS region. MK and EK contributed ecological and genetic expertise for the discussion, DW, JK and RJC provided genome data. MS set up the draft and all other authors reviewed and edited the manuscript.
- III. MCS collected, characterized and sequenced surveyed fungi, and inferred a phylogeny together with BT. Selected and additional strains were ordered and sent to MS for sequencing and chemical characterization of volatile profiles. Sequencing and antimicrobial testing at HZI in Braunschweig was done by CL. UB investigated volatile organic compound production, at which CL assisted. MB supervised the chemical characterization, KDH, ANM, JKJL, IP supervised the mycological characterisation by MCS and BT. ANM and JKJL provided taxonomical expertise. MCS and BT drafted the manuscript and all authors reviewed and edited the final manuscript assembled by MS, who supervised the whole project.
- IV. AYM screened and isolated the surveyed compounds, SEH aided with structure elucidation and supervised the chemical characterization by AYM. SA and WM provided the strain and SA examined nematicidal activities. CL examined anti cytoskeletal activities conveyed by the isolated chaetoglobosins and was supervised by TEBS. MS supervised and administered the project. The paper was drafted by AYM and all authors edited and reviewed the manuscript until SEH finalized it.
- V. KW supervised AC and NW in chemical screening and isolating surveyed metabolites produced by the fungal specimens isolated and morphologically characterized by EBS. AC sequenced the strains under supervision of LW. CL inferred a phylogeny of the Xylariaceae. LEP provided taxonomical expertise. MS conceptualized the study, KW drafted the manuscript and all authors reviewed and edited the text until completion by MS.
- VI. KB and JW chemically characterized the secondary metabolite production capabilities by the surveyed strain. This work was supervised by KB and sequencing supervised by CL, who inferred a molecular phylogeny. KB and

- CL drafted the manuscript, which MS finalized. The project was supervised by MS.
- VII. CW genetically modified the surveyed strain and isolated and characterized associated secondary metabolites. CW semi-synthetically derivatised the isolated compounds with help of MH. Both were supervised by EJS and RJC. CL investigated cytotoxic properties supervised by MS and anti cytoskeletal activities by TEBS and KR. Functional testing of the newly generated dyes was done by CL and supervised by KR. The manuscript was drafted by CW and RJC, all authors reviewed and edited the manuscript until completion by RJC, who supervised the whole project.
 - VIII. DW sequenced and analyzed genomic DNA and genomes supplied by EK, RJC, CS and BB supervised by CR and JK. CL inferred genome-level phylogenies from the analysis provided by DW. MS contributed taxonomic expertise, RJC provided chemical expertise. EK steered the analysis and together with DW drafted the manuscript for all authors to review and edit. The manuscript was finalized by EK.
 - IX. CL sequenced surveyed strains collected and isolated by MJP, CL, MCS, MS, and IKG and isolated stromatal constituents together with MJP. FS elucidated the structures. MJP and MCS morphologically characterized the specimens. MJP was supervised by SAK, IKG, HV and together with CL inferred phylogenies. CL made a chemotaxonomic comparison among all specimens and tested the isolated cytochalasin for actin disruptive capabilities, which was supervised by TEBS. CL and MJP drafted the manuscript, all authors reviewed and edited the text and MS finished the draft. The project as a whole was supervised by MS.
 - X. EGMA collected and preliminarily characterized the strains under supervision of SFK. LS and YMF morphologically characterized the strains and sequenced them. BMK extensively screened the strains for secondary metabolite production and isolated pure compounds and elucidated their structure under supervision of SFK. CL inferred phylogenies. BMK drafted the manuscript and CL, MS and YMF helped with finalizing it. MS provided taxonomic expertise, provided resources and helped with setting up the manuscript. The project as a whole was supervised by YMF.
 - XI. CP provided the strain. KYMG and MTJQ isolated the compounds and together with GP, AR, HMD, FS and APGM assigned the structure and stereochemistry to the compounds. KS and CL tested the compounds for anti-cytoskeletal properties under supervision of TEBS. The manuscript was drafted by KYMG and APGM and reviewed and edited by all authors. The project was supervised by MS and APGM.
 - XII. MJP collected and morphologically characterized surveyed strains under supervision of SAK, IKG and HV. CL and MJP sequenced the isolated strains. MJP and HV prepared phylogenetic inferences. The text was drafted by MJP and CL and finalized by MS, who contributed taxonomic expertise and supervised the project as a whole. All authors edited and reviewed the final manuscript.
 - XIII. MJP collected and morphologically characterized surveyed strains under supervision of SAK, IKG and HV. MJP, supervised by KW, and GE isolated

the compounds. FS and KW elucidated the structures. GP assigned the stereochemistry for the peptide. CL and MJP sequenced the isolated strains. MJP and HV prepared phylogenetic inferences. CL tested compounds for anti-actin cytoskeletal properties, supervised by TEBS and helped with administering the project. The text was drafted by MJP and CL, and finalized by MS, who contributed taxonomic expertise and supervised the project as a whole. All authors edited and reviewed the final manuscript.

- XIV. EGMA collected and preliminarily characterized the strains under supervision of SFK. LS and YMF morphologically characterized the strains and sequenced them. BMK helped to set up the manuscript and provided chemical expertise. CL inferred phylogenies and set up the draft together with YMF. All authors edited and reviewed the final manuscript.
- XV. CD provided the specimens, MCS isolated, morphologically characterized and sequenced the strains, and inferred a phylogeny. JJJ provided resources. ECG extracted stromata allowing chemotaxonomic comparison and molecular network analysis and was supervised by RF and MB. CL and MS advised MCS and ECG and helped setting up the draft with MCS and ECG. All authors edited and reviewed the final manuscript. MS supervised the project as a whole.
- XVI. EGMA collected and preliminarily characterized the strains under supervision of SFK. LS and YMF morphologically characterized the strains and sequenced them. BMK extensively screened the strains for secondary metabolite production and isolated pure compounds and elucidated their structure under supervision of SFK. CL inferred phylogenies. KS tested isolated compounds for anti-actin cytoskeletal properties and was supervised by TEBS. CL gave advice to KS. BMK and KS drafted the manuscript and CL, MS, TEBS and YFM helped to finalize it. MS provided taxonomic expertise and provided resources. The project as a whole was supervised by YMF.
- XVII. JAJ and EBS collected and morphologically characterized surveyed specimens. CL and EBS isolated the strains. RS sequenced and chemically characterized the strains allowing chemotaxonomic comparisons under supervision of CL. CL inferred a phylogeny and drafted the manuscript. MS provided resources, steered and supervised the project, and finalized the draft. All authors reviewed and edited the final manuscript.
- XVIII. DRH provided the strain and was supervised by MCA. CL screened the strain for secondary metabolite production capabilities and set up scale-up experiments. LS extracted and isolated compounds to purity following fermentation and extraction by CL. FS elucidated the structures. PS and CL sampled a scaled up production in 10L scale in a bioreactor and PS extracted and isolated derived compounds to purity. HZ tested anti-biofilm activities of isolated compounds and CL screened for anti-actin cytoskeletal activities and was supervised by TEBS and KR. MS and TEBS provided resources. CL set up the draft with help of LS and MS, and KR and MS finalized the draft. All authors reviewed and edited the final manuscript.
- XIX. AGTN, KDH and MS envisaged the review and defined different topic sections. CL and ECG contributed expertise in microbial drugs under

supervision of MS, SR in general mycology and ecology, PM in soil and forest biology, NT and AW in cultivation of fungi, MG and HS in broader biotechnological application of fungi as enzyme producers and for the generation of alternative biodegradable materials. AGTN drafted the manuscript and all authors contributed their expertise to expand and edit the paper. KDH and MS supervised the process and finalized the paper.

- XX. Strains were supplied by SKF. YMF morphologically characterized the strains and sequenced them. BMK extensively screened the strains for secondary metabolite production and isolated pure compounds and elucidated their structure under supervision of SKF. CL inferred phylogenies. BMK drafted the manuscript and CL, MS and YFM helped with finalizing it. MS provided taxonomic expertise and resources. The project as a whole was supervised by YMF.
- XXI. CL, KS, MK and KR envisaged the review. KS drafted a section covering structure activity relationships of cytochalasans, MK drafted a section covering direct interaction of cytochalasans with actin or actin dependent processes. CL advised KS and MK and helped drafting both sections, the introduction and the conclusion. CL and KR edited and reviewed the draft until finalization. TEBS contributed graphical representations of bioactivity. MS provided chemical and mycological expertise. Note: Both CL and KR share the corresponding authorship of the manuscript.
- XXII. MS envisaged the project. CL sequenced the strain. RS cultivated the strain and induced anamorph formation for MCS to characterize morphologically. HV and CL inferred phylogenies. MS, KB and CL prepared the formal taxonomic revision. CL and MS drafted the manuscript, all other authors reviewed and edited it until finalization by MS and CL.
- XXIII. MS conceptualized the study, and provided strains, MCS provided DNA for BV and JK for genome sequencing. BV analyzed raw data and MCS and TC extracted sequences from annotated genomes. MK and EK contributed ecological and genetic expertise for the discussion, RJC, MS provided resources. CL advised MCS and helped MCS to set up the draft. All authors reviewed and edited the manuscript and MS finalized it.
- XXIV. CL and MK performed wet experiments. AS, YT and HD helped with experiments and/or provided essential advice for experiments or data analysis. TEBS, PL, JF and PB provided essential reagents and/or helped with supervision. All authors analyzed and discussed data. CL, MK and KR interpreted the data and wrote the manuscript. All authors reviewed and edited the manuscript and KR finalized it.

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List of abbreviations

ABP	-	Actin Binding Protein
ATP	-	Adenosine Tri-phosphate
ADP	-	Adenosine Di-Phosphate
BNT	-	Binaphthalene-tetrol
DNA	-	Desoxynucleic acid
sp.	-	species
<i>nov.</i>	-	<i>nova</i>
NMR	-	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
NPF	-	Nucleation Promoting Factor
ITS	-	Internal transcribes spacer
LSU	-	Large Subunit
RPB2	-	RNA polymerase II gene
RNA	-	ribonucleic acid
TUB2	-	β -tubulin
WRC	-	WAVE-Regulatory Complex
Ena/VASP	-	Enabled / Vasodilator stimulated Phosphoprotein
MENA	-	Mammalian Enabled
Evl	-	Ena/VASP-like protein
CP	-	heterodimeric capping protein
WASP	-	Wiskott-Aldrich Syndrome Protein
N-WASP	-	Neuronal-Wiskott-Aldrich Syndrome Protein
EGFP	-	enhanced green fluorescent protein
SAR	-	Structure activity relationship
NRPS	-	Non-ribosomal peptide Synthethase
PKS	-	Polyketide Synthase

Summary

Global healthcare faces an ever-growing threat of resistance against commonly used antibiotics and the situation is dire considering that modern developing pipelines for antibiotics addressing new antibacterial targets are almost empty. Novel natural compounds or alternative strategies apart from pathogen eradication by chemotherapy with antibiotics may help confronting this issue. Organisms of the kingdom of fungi, and especially so members of the Ascomycota and Basidiomycota, have repeatedly emerged as talented chemical artists producing a vast diversity of bioactive compounds, which eventually even gave rise to the first antibiotic produced in industrial scale, penicillin. However, only a fraction of fungal biodiversity has been chartered and subjected to comprehensive taxonomical studies using modern state-of-the-art methodology, leaving fungal systematics in constant change. This combined with the fact that most fungal species were actually never subjected to systematic natural product discovery campaigns clearly shows that many more compounds with unprecedented and interesting bioactivities are to be isolated and characterized in the future. Cytochalasans are a group of hybrid secondary metabolites produced across different orders of the Ascomycota most widely known for their actin inhibitory activity. However, in spite of over 400 described members of this compound family, a sound structure activity relationship is lacking, impeding its biotechnological exploitation as potential anti-infective probably useful for interference with actin-dependent pathogen invasion into host (e.g. human) cells. Moreover, the precise molecular mechanisms of action of this family of compounds and derived implications for actin-dependent processes have so far remained obscure. This thesis includes taxonomic surveys of different members of the Xylariales and Diaporthales and their related potential as producers of known and novel natural products, with special emphasis on cytochalasans and their characterization regarding anti-actin bioactivity. Furthermore, in this thesis I explored the interference of cytochalasin B and D with the actin polymerization machinery using mouse melanoma cells as model system. In this study, it was shown that different actin regulators distinctly react to cytochalasin B treatment and that cytochalasin B-dependent accumulation of one of these prominent factors, VASP, an actin polymerase commonly located at the leading edge of protruding lamellipodia, is dependent on the presence of heterodimeric capping protein. Furthermore, functionalized cytochalasin H derivatives generated following a mutasynthetic approach were explored for their retained actin disruptive capabilities,

laying the foundation for an engineering platform for on-demand creation of hand-tailored cytochalasans.

Introduction

Natural Products and their producers

For centuries, human kind has been harnessing other organisms to improve survival chances in the everlasting peril of life, be it to serve as workhorses for crafting and manufacturing (such as cattle in agriculture; Teletchea 2019), as food (such as domesticated animals, plants and microorganisms; Abbo et al. 2017; Steensels et al. 2019; Teletchea 2019), or therapeutic purposes. Use of plants and fungi are historically well-recorded for medicinal purposes and served as basis for the development of distinct traditions across different cultures throughout a series of trial and error (Fabricant and Farnsworth 2001; Poucheret et al. 2006). Noteworthy, successful reports stem from e.g. ancient Egyptian and Chinese cultures using moldy food to treat topical skin infections (Wainwright 1989). In Chinese culture, it is common practice in the framework of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) to use mushrooms as remedies and to aid with recovery of patients following illness (Wang et al. 2017). Even in Europe, the famous mummified iceman ‘Ötzi’ carried a specimen of the birch polypore *Fomitopsis betulina* and a fern identified as *Pteridium aquilinum* with him, hypothesized to serve as a kind of self-medication due to the mushrooms angiostatic and the ferns anti-parasitic properties (Zink and Maixner 2019; Zink et al. 2019). Irrespective of the latter archeological interpretations being true or not, the aforementioned records still demonstrate historically early-reaching examples of biomedical usage of foraged plants and fungi. Technological improvements and developments, especially in the field of chemical spectroscopy, later enabled the correlation of this ancient knowledge with the factors that actually convey the beneficiary effects that are ascribed to medicinal plants and mushrooms. These factors have been termed natural products, regularly produced as secondary metabolites, substances with an astonishing chemical diversity and broad range of biological activity (Atanasov et al. 2021). In contrast to primary metabolites, secondary metabolites are not existential for the survival for the producing organism, but are instead thought to serve as enhancers of competitiveness in a given natural habitat (Keller 2019). For example, secondary metabolite production can be rationalized as a form of defense mechanism to prevent ingestion by predators (e.g. toxins in plants, Harborne 2007; and mushrooms, Yin et al. 2019), but can also serve to fend-off competitors in a scenario of chemical warfare to conquer and maintain access to carbon sources (Hiscox and Boddy 2017).

Notwithstanding, the precise reason why a given compound is produced, *i.e.* its ecological function, is not trivial to decipher, as it is difficult to manipulate secondary metabolism to test hypotheses *in situ*. However, assumptions can be made by using comparative approaches, or correlating bioactivities of a substance with the lifestyle of a producer (Schmidt et al. 2019).

That this knowledge is not solely of academic interest is exemplified by the probably widest known example of a secondary metabolite developed into a therapeutic drug, the penicillins. The antibacterial properties of a *Penicillium rubens* strain (Houbraken et al. 2011) were noticed and reported by Fleming in 1929 in co-culture with *Staphylococcus aureus*, on which the fungus exhibited inhibitory effects (Fleming 1929; Demain and Sanchez 2009). This effect was then attributed to the production of antibacterials derived of the penicillins, which turned out as a starting point to develop modern antibiotics to treat potentially lethal bacterial infectious diseases (Demain and Sanchez 2009).

Initially developed based on bioactivities tested in laboratory scale, or even from observations following human ingestion (if considering ethnopharmacologic-based drug discovery), natural products continually served as foundation for leads in drug development. Two examples, amongst others, for natural products described from the kingdom of plants would be the digitoxins and paclitaxel, isolated from *Digitalis purpurea* and *Taxus brevifolia*, respectively. Digitoxins are toxic substances, however, proved to be useful if carefully administered and are still used today to treat heart failure, albeit with an extremely narrow therapeutic window (Whayne 2018). Paclitaxel, on the other hand, was isolated and described from needles gathered from yew trees and is marketed under the name Taxol® for treatment of cancer (Donehower 1996). One example for an important class of antibacterials developed from a bacterial isolate of *Streptomyces* are the carbapenems such as tebipenempivoxil, used to combat bacterial infections with multi-drug resistant Staphylococci and pseudomonades (Papp-Wallace et al. 2011). A few examples for important fungal-derived natural products developed into drugs are the anthelmintic emodepside, the pleuromutilins, cyclosporine A and the statins, amongst others. Briefly, emodepside is the only endophyte-derived drug on the market and is produced from semi-synthetic derivatization of PF1022A, a cyclooctadepsipeptide first described and patented from a sterile mycelium of an endophytic *Rosellinia* isolate (Scherkenbeck et al. 2002). The

pleuromutilines have been known for decades and have only now been developed into a marketable drug due to significant improvements in product yield (Bailey et al. 2016; Mapook et al. 2022). Cyclosporin A is used in the clinical setting to prevent rejection of organ transplants by suppressing the immune system of the recipient, which eventually revolutionized transplantation medicine (Survase et al. 2011). The statins are used to modulate blood cholesterol, effectively saving millions of lives due to improving the state of care for cardiovascular diseases (Endo 2008; Stossel 2008) and are considered among the critical drugs (Willis 2018). However, it is usually not until further improvements, such as the reduction of toxic side effects, improved selectivity or efficacy by e.g. semi-synthetic derivatization campaigns until lead compounds are suited for clinical testing and application (Cragg and Newman 2013; Guo 2017). Mycophenolic acid, described from *Penicillium brevicompactum*, was only used in clinical care once reduction of toxic side effects by semi-synthetic derivatization allowed its application as immunosuppressant (Bentley 2000). Cephalosporins, originally isolated from *Acremonium*, are used as broad-spectrum antibacterials and are now on the market in their fifth generation, only thanks to steady improvement of selectivity and efficacy (Lin and Kück 2022). A more detailed list of aforementioned drugs and their economic importance on the market has been reviewed and published ahead of this work and can be read in more detail in study XIX appended to this thesis. Other applications involving natural products besides their role as pharmaceuticals involve their usage in plant protection (compounds such as the strobilurines, Sauter et al. 1999) or as additives to prevent food spoilage (Stadler et al. 2012), amongst others. The natural product-derived drugs listed here are only a small subsection of all approved and marketed ones across the different systematic kingdoms of life (Newman and Cragg 2020), but demonstrate the significant impact on everyday human in modern society.

Figure 1: Structures of a selection of important natural products discussed in the previous section.

If focusing on the vast success of natural products as drugs to combat infectious diseases, one has to notice that the majority of lead structures have been discovered decades ago and are still being explored today (Davies 2006). Notwithstanding this, the rate of discovery of novel leads with new modes of action to combat the rising occurrence of antimicrobial resistances has been scant (Miethke et al. 2021). In part, this has been discussed to be due to high-costs associated with the development of antibiotics with a comparably low return of investment (Årdal et al. 2020). It is clear by now, that the time period some have described as the “Golden Age of Antibiotics” is ending and that their extensive and careless use in human and animal healthcare probably only accelerated resistance emergence (Pandey et al. 2024). This threatens the achievements that were made possible by antibiotics to treat and combat infectious diseases (Davies 2006). As it is only a matter of time until humankind regresses to a point where once treatable bacterial infections become untreatable again, increasing attention is focusing on how to reverse this trend, to keep the economic cost of illness and potentially avoidable deaths at bay (Miethke et al. 2021).

In order to identify new lead candidates, a commonly applied first-line strategy consists of simply screening discovered and isolated substances for growth inhibitory effects in screening campaigns. Other potential sought-after bioactivities constitute the reduction of pathogenicity restricting harmful effects exerted by pathogens, prevention of invasion into host cells or strengthening the innate immunity against bacterial and viral invasion (de la Fuente-Nunez et al. 2023). Screening for bioactivity requires substantial amounts of a given natural product, which constitutes a rate limiting parameter. If produced in culture under laboratory conditions, natural products are frequently only isolated in milligram ranges. If directly isolated from environmental sources, sustainable production is often impossible and effectively prohibits straight-forward upscale of production (Atanasov et al. 2021). This, besides other reasons, severely limits their free addition to screening libraries to search for bioactivity and access for further development by e.g. semi synthesis. Adding to this, a vast chemical diversity of natural products remains to be discovered, comprising new chemical scaffolds or undescribed derivatives, especially from untapped taxonomic sources (Kuephadungphan et al. 2021). Finding and testing new core scaffolds or derivatives increases chances to discover unprecedented targets and bioactivities, or may give information about important chemical moieties mediating bioactivity (structure activity relationship, SAR; Hellwig and Stadler 2004; Grabowski et al. 2008).

Recreating these scaffolds, irrespective of novelty, in a bottom-up total synthesis approach is a daunting task for chemists and often takes several years, if not decades, to complete, if possible at all (Atanasov et al. 2021). Hence, it appears fruitful to return to the producing organisms from which natural product-derived drugs were originally described. It may appear feasible to add animals to the list of potential reservoirs for bioactive substances with industrial applicability, however, only time will tell if this approach will be fruitful or not (Lüddecke et al. 2023; Lüddecke and Blank 2024).

The Kingdom of Fungi

Fungi are eukaryotes that are considered as an own, independent kingdom which segregated 1 billion years ago from a shared lineage with the Animalia (Samarakoon et al. 2016). A long time treated as plants (and still administered by the botanical code of conduct, probably owing to the close relationship of fungi and deceptive similarities of stalk-forming mushrooms in the field), it took until the introduction of molecular phylogenetic techniques that settled their more close relationship with animals than with plants (Willis 2018). The kingdom of fungi is currently segregated into 16 phyla, of which the Ascomycota and the Basidiomycota comprise by far the most species rich ones to date (Wijayawardene et al. 2020; Dai et al. 2022). Fungi form multicellular and interconnected networks of mono, bi- or multinuclear, interconnected or septated hyphae that are equipped with pores in different complexity (He et al. 2019). All fungi contain chitin in their cell wall and are heterotrophic, feeding either on living or dead organic matter (Willis 2018) and may enter symbiotic relationships as mutualists or parasitize other organisms as antagonists (Selosse et al. 2022). Lifestyle and cellular organization of fungi differ significantly across the different phyla and fulfill a wide set of specialized ecological roles as saprobes, parasites and pathogens (Zanne et al. 2020). Members of both phyla are frequently shown to be able to reproduce sexually (teleomorph) and asexually (anamorph) via conspicuous structures, ranging from stalk-like (e.g. cap- or cup forming fungi of the Agaricales; Lodge et al. 2014, or Pezizales; Ekanayaka et al. 2018, respectively) to microscopic fruiting bodies (e.g. teliospore containing telia formed by rust fungus; Kirschner and Okuda 2013, and ascospores formed in ascoma; Janošík et al. 2023). Anamorph structures are often small and not visible to the naked eye and comprise conidiogenous structures forming conidiospores by mitotic division (Visagie et al. 2016). Both teleomorph and anamorph structures

were historically important parameters for species identification and description. Of note, it was common practice to systematize pleomorphic fungi shown to form both structures with two distinct generic names (dual-nomenclature). This practice was only abandoned 2011 (Hawksworth 2011), but still affects modern taxonomy today as new anamorph-teleomorph pairs are uncovered and formally unified, with priority regularly given to the older name (Rossman et al. 2015).

Ascomycota and Basidiomycota are accounted towards featuring the most prolific producers of secondary metabolites in the fungal kingdom (Bills and Gloer 2016). This fact is exploited both by natural product scientists searching for new compounds and taxonomists in the framework of chemotaxonomy, as secondary metabolite production patterns were frequently shown to be specific for distinct taxonomic lineages (Frisvad et al. 2008). A fungal order of the Ascomycota, in which chemotaxonomy is applied with great success in tandem with morphological and genetic characterization in a polyphasic framework is comprised of the Xylariales.

Xylariales

The Xylariales belong to the Sordariomycetes and were composed of 20 families in 2021 (Dai et al. 2022), albeit the number fluctuates as additional taxa are added towards phylogenetic data matrices depicting the phylogenetic tree of life (compare Samarakoon et al. 2020 and study XXII published over the course of this work). Members of the order usually feature thick-walled, well-developed perithecial ascomata embedded into well-developed stromata that harbor eight-spored unitunicate asci that react with bluing in presence of iodide-containing Melzers reagent (amyloid reaction positive, J+) at their apical apparatus (Smith et al. 2003). They are ubiquitously distributed as saprobes, parasites, pathogens and endophytes with the highest diversity reported from the tropics and have attracted considerable interest as resource for the discovery of new and bioactive secondary metabolites (Helaly et al. 2018; Becker and Stadler 2021). Teleomorph morphology of this group share a considerable overlap, which complicated a clear-cut systematic approach for decades (Jaklitsch et al. 2016). An anamorph-based classification system first used by Ju & Rogers (1996) separating the pigment containing 'hypoxyloid' taxa, forming nodulisporium-like anamorphs from 'xylarioid' taxa developing geniculosporium-like anamorphs turned out to be a more reliable compass to infer intergeneric relationships.

Evidence gathered from pigment chemistry, secondary metabolite analysis across the Hypoxylaceae and multigene sequencing coupled with molecular phylogenetic inference later further corroborated this notion. Over the course of the last comprehensive polyphasic analysis of the systematic status of the Xylariaceae by Wendt et al. (2018), the 'hypoxyloid' taxa were emended and raised to family level (Hypoxylaceae), while the xylarioid taxa remained in the Xylariaceae *sensu stricto*. Concordantly, *Pyrenopolyporus* was erected to accommodate specimens with long, tubular perithecia. Other genera like *Biscogniauxia* and *Camillea* were placed in a sister clade with *Graphostroma platystomum* resolving in a separate lineage from Hypoxylaceae and Xylariaceae, which were subsequently summarized under the Graphostromataceae. However, the phylogenetic backbone was reportedly far from being well resolved. Only one year later, a report of newly collected Argentinian specimens related to *Hypoxylon monticulosum* emerged as a separate clade in the previously published Hypoxylaceae backbone, which led Lambert et al. (2019) to erect *Hypomontagnella* as a new genus, based on phylogenetic and chemical data. Mature specimens of *Hypomontagnella* usually lack a visible pigment reaction when stromata material is submerged in 10% KOH. Moreover, isolated strains were so far the only ones to show sporothriolide production in culture, which was determined as a key-phenotype for this genus when compared to other members of the family (Lambert et al. 2019). This demonstrates how dynamic taxonomic systematics can be, once decisive, new information is acquired and analyzed in tandem with previously reported data. With the implementation of full-genome sequencing, comparative genomics and phylogenomic techniques, it is to be expected that borders of this order will be further refined, enabling an increasingly natural classification of its biodiversity.

As a proxy until sophisticated genomics-associated tools are established in sufficient quality, chemotaxonomic approaches may help where classical or even polyphasic concepts have so far failed to resolve taxonomic boundaries. Specifically, the co-occurrence of distinct metabolites in combination with each other is often highly informative to infer species or generic relationships. Carneic acid A and B, for example, have so far only been described from stromata of *Hypoxylon carneum* (Quang et al. 2006; Wendt et al. 2018). Sporothriolide production has originally been described from a *Sporothrix* strain (Krohn et al. 1994), but neither its taxonomic identity nor the production could be resolved in a later paper re-examining the strain (Surup et al. 2014). This leaves the aforementioned genus *Hypomontagnella* the only extant

source of this type of compounds known today (Surup et al. 2014; Lambert et al. 2019). The chemotaxonomic concept is also applied with large success in the genera *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium*. Here, chemical markers are evaluated to designate the safety of important biotechnological workhorses for the production of food, such as cheese and food additives like citric acid (Nielsen et al. 2009; Frisvad et al. 2018). Conceptually, the production of a secondary metabolite is ultimately a direct reflection of genetic information, rendering it a valuable tool for specimen characterization (Kuhnert et al. 2021).

The Hypoxylaceae have been described to show a rich abundance of chemical diversity and variety, both in their natural habitat and in laboratory culture. The teleomorph of members of this family usually feature a carbonized structure in which its perithecia are embedded, the stroma (Wendt et al. 2018). Here, many Hypoxylaceae tend to store impressive amounts of extractable pigments, rendering them useful for chemotaxonomic comparisons, but also for searching novel, bioactive secondary metabolites (Stadler et al. 2007). These minute amounts of extracted compounds are useful in analytical scale, but too scarce for larger biotechnological exploitation. This notwithstanding, the chances that these metabolites serve specialized functions in nature is high. This idea is further nourished by the finding that not only the amount, but also secondary metabolite composition was shown to change upon stromata ontogeny, with occurrence of cytochalasins – colorless, cytotoxic compounds – in young and shifting towards a larger proportion composed of pigments in older stromata (Stadler et al. 2006). An example for cytochalasin production serving an ecologically important mechanism would be the host tissue invasion of *Pyricularia grisea*, a phytopathogen of the crabb grass. Here, cytochalasin production was shown to be essential for plant tissue invasion (Tsurushima et al. 2005). However, as *Hypoxylon* species tend to grow on diseased plants and as saprobes on dead wood, an aggressive role of cytochalasin production against the host can be ruled out. Other ideas revolve around its deposition in stromal tissue as an act in defense *versus* predators instead (Stadler et al. 2006). Other pigments of the rubiginosin family, produced by members of the ‘red *Hypoxylon*’ circumscribed in the *H. rubiginosum* complex, have been shown to inhibit biofilms of *Staphylococcus aureus*, underpinning potential, ecological roles of these compounds to improve survival and fitness. As opposed to the rubiginosins, which so far have only been isolated from stromata,

cytochalasins are readily produced in culture by a vast amount of different species throughout the Ascomycota.

Cytochalasans

The cytochalasans are secondary metabolites biologically synthesized in a concerted action by a non-ribosomal peptide synthetase (NRPS) and a polyketide synthase (PKS; Skellam 2017). The vast majority of cytochalasans has so far been described from *Aspergillus* (aspochalasins) and *Penicillium*, but have also been described from *Metarhizium*, Diaporthaceae (diaporthalasin), Magnaporthaceae, Hypoxylaceae and Xylariaceae, to name a few (Zhu et al. 2021). The core structure is commonly presumed to consist of a tricyclic backbone connected to a NRPS-dependent amino acid-derived moiety that is often name-giving for the trivial name (such as cytochalasins, chaetoglobosins and aspochalasins being derived from phenylalanine, tryptophan and isoleucine, respectively). An iso-indolone core is thought to form upon intramolecular Diels-Alder cyclization with the PKS-derived fatty acid chain, yielding a larger macrocycle in the same step (Skellam 2017). First isolated in the 60s, cytochalasan chemodiversity now spans over 400 individual described structures, comprising both substances of synthetic and biological origin (Zhu et al. 2021). Structural variety mainly appears for the incorporated amino acid, the size and variety of the macrocycle (e.g. carbocyclic or lactone as in cytochalasin B) and the oxidative configuration of the former and the attached iso-indolone core.

Figure 2: Structure of cytochalasin H. The amino-acid and PKS-derived moieties are shown in dark blue and cyan, respectively. Functional groups colored in red were shown to be manipulated or introduced in subsequent tailoring steps involving different oxidases in the biosynthesis of the compound in *Pyricularia grisea* NI980 by Wang et al. (2019b).

Cytochalasans are most widely known for their bioactivity exerted on eukaryotic cells. First described effects on tissue culture cells involved reports of induced

multinucleation (Krishan and Ray-Chaudhuri 1969). This effect was later traced back to their ability to inhibit cell division by interfering with the polymerization of intracellular microfilaments, actin filaments (Schroeder 1970; Spudich and Lin 1972). Back then, this observation proved the independence of cellular and nuclear division and heralded their extensive use as tool compounds in cell biology (Peterson and Mitchison 2002). Since then, they have been used in thousands of studies (see also review in study XXI published in the course of this work).

Apart from their role as tools in science, cytochalasins have been discussed as pathogenicity factors in the context of plant-fungus interactions. Indeed, many cytochalasins have been reported in genera featuring important phytopathogens, such as *Dematophora necatrix*, the causative agent of white fruit rot and producer of cytochalasin E (Kanematsu et al. 1997) or the genus *Diaporthe*, a complicated genus featuring many phytopathogens affecting vineyards (Chepkirui and Stadler 2017). However, production of a cytochalasin was rarely reported to be essential for phytopathogenicity, with the previously mentioned *P. grisea* infecting *Digitaria* grass as a noteworthy exception (Tsurushima et al. 2005). Apart from this example, cytochalasin production can probably be regarded as auxiliary factor for host invasion rather than facilitator.

Despite the huge structural variety reported so far, a clear-cut structure activity relationship is not yet described (Scherlach et al. 2010; Skellam 2017; Zhu et al. 2021). A recent paper even reported on undescribed inhibitory capacities exerted by few cytochalasins on biofilms formed by *Staphylococcus aureus*, an important, opportunistic pathogen frequently causing complications in infected individuals (Yuyama et al. 2018). Biofilms are aggregates of secreted extracellular proteins formed by different organisms, serving as habitat for multiple different species, outside in natural environments, but also inside of larger organisms such as humans (de la Fuente-Nunez et al. 2023). These biofilms act as protective surroundings, e.g. inhibiting free diffusion of antibiotics into deeper biofilm layers or protecting the cell-mass from immune system responses. Given that cytochalasins were shown to affect actin dynamics and that eukaryotic actin is not present in bacteria, potential targets comprise similarly folded bacterial actin-like proteins, but this is pure speculation as its precise target, to the best of my knowledge, is unknown.

The eukaryotic actin cytoskeleton and cytochalasans

The best-studied target of cytochalasans is actin, the central component of the eukaryotic actin cytoskeleton. Actin occurs in six distinct isoforms in mammals (Perrin and Ervasti 2010). These comprise α -skeletal, cardiac and smooth muscle actin (actA1, actA2, actC1), β -cytosolic actin (actB) and γ -smooth muscle and cytosolic actin (actG1, actG2). Deletion of all, but actG1 has been shown to be lethal in a mouse model system (Perrin and Ervasti 2010), while loss of actG1 has been shown to be associated with progressive hearing loss in adolescence (Perrin and Ervasti 2010). Expression of actin isoforms is tissue specific, but how and if this is connected to them contributing to potential, distinct and specialized roles is only poorly understood (Simiczjew et al. 2017).

Actin monomers are capable of self-organizing into multimers, and subsequently polymerize into polarized filaments *in vitro* in physiological salt conditions with both ends possessing distinct reaction kinetics for the attachment of new monomers (Pollard 2016). Actin monomers can bind ATP and slowly hydrolyze ATP to ADP, affecting their association and dissociation kinetics from the so-called plus- (or barbed-) and minus- (or pointed-) ends of filaments. The terms barbed and pointed end derive from structural data upon myosin subfragment 1 binding and refer to the rapidly and slowly growing end, respectively (Huxley 1963; Woodrum et al. 1975). Polymerisation is concentration-dependent and thus influenced by the pool of available monomers. If monomer concentration falls below or exceeds a specific value, net-elongation or net-depolymerization of actin filaments in solution takes place, which has been coined critical concentration. Thermodynamically, the critical concentration represents the quotient of the association and dissociation rate at each end and for both, ADP- and ATP-bound actin (Pollard 2016). In cells, actin-binding proteins (ABPs) tightly regulate filament assembly and disassembly both spatially and temporally, allowing actin filament initiation (called nucleation) and elongation at specific sites. In addition, they are governing filament turnover by balancing continuous polymerization and depolymerization of mature actin filaments (Cooper and Schafer 2000; Rottner et al. 2017; Lappalainen et al. 2022). Other factors (such as profilins) bind monomers to specifically supply them for specialized actin polymerases (Kovar et al. 2006). Actin filaments are further organized into higher order structures with the help of ABPs to e.g. form stress-fibers – anti-parallel bundles of actin filaments of varying size (Tojkander et al. 2012) – or networks of cross-linked actin filaments commonly found

at cell ruffles – ‘ruffled’ protrusions of plasma membrane (Schaks et al. 2019) – or the cell periphery. Peripheral actin networks are also called lamellipodia and constitute thin, quasi-two dimensional sheets of plasma membrane containing crosslinked actin filament networks with associated factors. Lamellipodia at their base and further proximal, specific actin filament structures such as stress fibers are interconnected with a network of focal adhesions (Small et al. 2002; Schaks et al. 2019). The latter multi-protein complexes, together with integrins, act as ‘anchors’ through the plasma membrane, connecting the cytoplasm of cells with the underlying substrate, enabling the projection of pushing and pulling forces through lamellipodial networks at the cell front and contractile bundles at the rear, respectively. Tight coordination of front pushing and rear pulling, regulated by transient, focal force exertions onto the substratum facilitate efficient cell migration, at least the mesenchymal mode of this process (Lämmermann and Sixt 2009; Charras and Sahai 2014; Revach et al. 2020). Other, actin-dependent structures known to be associated with different types of migration (such as in neuronal growth cones) or with other processes, such as pathfinding or pathogen invasion are filopodia – bundles of actin filaments commonly found at the cell periphery (Small and Rottner 2010). Filopodia form finger-like protrusions, which can occur embedded into or independent of lamellipodial actin networks. In fish keratocytes and murine mouse models, filopodia-like structures embedded into lamellipodia have been named microspikes (Small and Rottner 2010).

The high degree of organization and flexibility that this orchestrated system – and actin binding factors governing this machinery – conveys is essential for a plethora of processes, that includes cell division and migration, as mentioned above, but extends to other prominent phenomena, including endocytosis and trafficking, organelle biogenesis, autophagy or even transcription and translation, just to name a few (Rottner et al. 2017). Cytochalasans have been found to interfere with actin-dependent processes by interfering with monomer addition at the barbed end of actin filaments (Cooper 1987). At sufficiently high concentrations, the formerly described highly organized actin structures deteriorate, essentially leading to total collapse of the actin cytoskeleton (see for example Kretz et al. 2019). This effect, however, has been shown to be reversible for some, but not all, cytochalasans (Yahara et al. 1982; Kretz et al. 2019). The reasons for this behavior and for partly differential functions of given cytochalasans (see below) are not understood.

Due to their ascribed role as actin cytoskeletal disruptors, cytochalasins have been discussed as potential drugs in the context of anti-cancer treatment as cytotoxins, cytostatics or anti-migratory compounds inhibiting metastasis (Trendowski 2015). However, expectable side effects are dimming expectations, since cytochalasins, if used as they are, would affect healthy cells with unforeseeable consequences (apart from acute toxicity) as well. Preparing these compounds for drug development would require a sound knowledge of their structure activity relationship (SAR) and careful steering of their bioactivities by chemical modification, allowing their therapeutic usage. However, SAR campaigns published so far have remained inconclusive, as distinct campaigns reported over time have only shared partial overlap and covered only a handful of all described cytochalasins. More comprehensive work has so far been hampered by the fact that the majority of cytochalasins are not commercially available and access to producing strains is limited (also discussed and summarized in review XXI). Moreover, another severe limitation of estimating the applicability of cytochalasins as potential drugs lays in the fact that research has so far only focused on a handful of different cytochalasins, of which cytochalasins B and D have been used by far the most. A summary of the literature covering these topics has been published in a review ahead of this thesis (XXI). Finally, yet importantly, most knowledge describing cytochalasin bioactivity and the corresponding mode of action stems from papers from the 1970ies and -80ies, focusing mostly on *in vitro* experiments (Cooper 1987). How precisely distinct actin regulators shape different actin structures *in situ*, however, is being systematically unraveled only recently, with lots of open questions and issues. If and how cytochalasins interfere with this complicated regulatory network has not been carefully addressed so far (compare with study XXI).

Actin nucleation and regulation machinery in protrusion

As pointed out in the previous section, nucleation of new actin filaments and subsequent polymerization is exquisitely controlled in and restricted to specific subcellular localities (reviewed by e.g. Rottner et al. 2017). Nucleation of new filaments embedded into a growing network is achieved by specialized proteins, the so-called nucleation promoting factors (NPFs), such as the Wiskott-Aldrich Syndrome protein (WASP) family specific for the hematopoietic system (Alekhina et al. 2017).

Biochemically, WASP family proteins share a set of conserved domains described as verprolin (also called WASP homology 2 domain, WH2) and cofilin homology (more recently central instead of cofilin homology) domains (V, C) and multiple residues of acidic amino acids (A), forming the highly conserved VCA (or WCA) module and a more N-terminal proline-rich region called poly-proline domain (Miki and Takenawa 1998; Stradal et al. 2004; Campellone and Welch 2010). Over time, at least seven additional orthologues were described, the ubiquitously expressed, but neuronally enriched N-WASP (hence its name), three isogenes of WASP family verprolin-homologous protein (WAVE; Miki et al. 1998), WAVE1, 2 and 3, also known as Scar from its original name in *Dictyostelium* (Bear et al. 1998), as well as the WASP Scar Homologue (WASH), the WASP homolog associated with actin, membranes and microtubules (WHAMM) and the junction-mediating regulatory protein (JMY; Campellone and Welch 2010; Alekhina et al. 2017). All of them share the formerly described domains with variable numbers of the W-domain at their C-termini and largely distinct modes of regulation mediated by their N-termini. Best studied to date are WASP and N-WASP, which harbor a canonical GTPase-binding domain (GBD), also called CRIB (Cdc42; Cell Division Cycle 42 – and Rac; Ras-related C3 botulinum toxin substrate), well established to serve as activation module by the small Rho-family (Ras homology) GTPase Cdc42. Moreover, N-WASP and WASP share another homologous domain termed WASP homology 1 domain (WH1) and a highly homologous, whereas WAVEs instead harbor the so-called WAVE homologous domain (WHD). Both WH1 and WHD are thought to serve as protein interaction interfaces, mediating binding of regulatory proteins, such as WASP-interacting protein (WIP) for N-WASP and WASP or the scaffolding of WAVE with other proteins to form multimeric complexes (further elaborated on below; Rottner et al. 2021). The regulation of WASH, WHAMM and JMY is not yet fully understood (Alekhina et al. 2017). WAVE, instead, is incorporated into a heteropentameric protein complex, the WAVE Regulatory Complex (WRC), consisting of in total five different subunits comprising tissue specific orthologues (Rottner et al. 2021). All WASP family proteins fulfill specific roles in conveying signal cascade information to shape and steer the actin cytoskeleton, eliciting specific functions (Alekhina et al. 2017; Bieling and Rottner 2023). In all cases, it is thought that WASP family interaction with its interactors positively regulates subsequent activation of a hetero-heptameric protein complex containing two actin related proteins and five smaller subunits (Arp2/3 complex). This

Arp2/3 complex acts as a starting point for a new daughter filament from a pre-existing mother filament (Machesky et al. 1994, 1997; Mullins et al. 1998), enabling the creation of branched actin networks.

Besides this complex, another family of factors promoting nucleation and actin polymerization are formins. Formins themselves are auto-inhibited and upon activation, actively polymerase actin filaments as dimers. Activated formins are capable of both driving de-novo nucleation of actin filaments and promoting their elongation (Pruyne et al. 2002). Contrasting Arp2/3 complex activity, formin-elongated actin filaments are not branched and elongated in a linear fashion, which has been shown, e.g., to contribute to mechanical stability and force development in lamellipodial protrusions (Kage et al. 2017). Unlike Arp2/3 complex, formins were shown not to be essential for the formation of lamellipodia (Wu et al. 2012). Many other factors were described to be tightly interconnected as well, but not essential for lamellipodia formation, prominent examples of which include the Enabled/Vasodilator stimulated phosphoprotein (Ena/VASP) and heterodimeric capping protein (CP), to only name two (Damiano-Guercio et al. 2020; Funk et al. 2021). Ena/VASP family proteins comprise three orthologues in mammals and have been shown to be associated with efficient cell edge protrusion by acting as actin filament elongases in lamellipodia and in focal adhesions, although they are not essential for either process (Damiano-Guercio et al. 2020; Faix and Rottner 2022). Heterodimeric capping protein, on the other hand, exerts a contrary role by capping actin filaments and inhibiting further monomer addition to barbed ends (Blanchoin et al. 2000). How Arp2/3 complex and associated signaling as well as other actin nucleators, elongators and cappers are interconnected, is only in the process of being uncovered, for instance following the advent of efficient genome editing enabled by clustered regularly interspaced palindromic repeats (CRISPR) / CRISPR associated (cas) technology.

[Regulation and polymerization of Arp2/3 complex-dependent networks and their dissection using CRISPR/Cas9 technology](#)

Predating the usage of CRISPR / Cas9 technology, the functions of distinct actin binding proteins have already been studied in great biochemical detail (Lappalainen et al. 2022). One example amongst many would be proteins of the Ena/VASP family

(reviewed by Faix and Rottner 2022). These were shown to contain three major domains: an Ena/VASP homology domain 1 (EVH1) and 2 (EVH 2) and a proline rich domain. The EVH2 domain contains a G-actin binding (GAB) WH2 and an F-actin binding (FAB) motif, together with a domain characterized to be essential for Ena/VASP tetramerization. However, to what extent individual motifs are required for correct subcellular positioning has until recently remained unclear. A cell system devoid of all functional Ena/Vasp family members (Damiano-Guercio et al. 2020) allowed to tackle this question. Faix and Rottner could show that the isolated and GFP-tagged EVH1 domain was localized correctly and independently of the full-length actin binding EVH2 domain (Faix and Rottner 2022), which was previously assumed to be essential for lamellipodial targeting (Loureiro et al. 2002), as long as the tetramerization domain was present. In other words, that the EVH2 domain is dispensable for targeting of Ena/VASP proteins could only be unequivocally confirmed in a knockout system, in which tetramerization-mediated targeting by endogenous proteins could be excluded.

In *in vitro* experiments, purified full-length Ena/VASP was shown to accelerate actin filament growth in the presence of G-actin in a fashion sensitive to actin filament capping by CP (Breitsprecher et al. 2008). CP, in turn, is composed of two subunits (α - and β) that upon heterodimerization are able to bind to actin filament barbed ends with nanomolar affinity, effectively inhibiting further addition of monomers (Maun et al. 1996; Yamashita et al. 2003). When kept in solution, even minor amounts of CP are able to abrogate filament elongation by Ena/VASP, but this was not observed upon experimental clustering of Ena/VASP proteins e.g. on beads, effectively blocking the capping mediated by CP (Breitsprecher et al. 2008). These observations demonstrate that the function and role of distinct actin regulators can be highly context-dependent. In other words: unidimensional data acquired from biochemical experiments have so far probably underestimated the role and function of distinct actin regulators. Such activities hence need to be studied in their original environment, *in situ*, while exerting their function, which is contributing to the shaping of actin architecture and cellular morphology. Due to the advent of CRISPR/Cas9 technology, loss-of-function studies and genetic manipulation have become much more feasible, enabling on-demand genome editing. First described as an integral part of an adaptive immune system in bacteria against phage infections, CRISPR / Cas9 workflows introduce guide sequences that serves as specific templates directing nuclease activity of the Cas9 protein complex to specific sites within the genome, such as exon 1 or 2 of the gene

of choice encoding given actin binding protein (Doudna and Charpentier 2014; Manghwar et al. 2019). After successive, Cas9-mediated double strand breaks, both ends are repaired by non-homologous end joining, which eventually leads to the introduction or removal of nucleotides of variable lengths potentially effecting reading frame shifts for inserts and deletions in multiples of one and two. This effectively yields disruption of the reading frame of given genes, and hence elimination of protein expression and loss of function. This has been employed with great success in the field of cell biology, even allowing the deletion of multiple genes in succession (Kage et al. 2017, 2022; Damiano-Guercio et al. 2020; Hakala et al. 2021; Hein et al. 2023; Pokrant et al. 2023).

Specifically, application of this strategy to study actin assembly and the role of distinct actin-associated regulators enabled in-depth insights into the intriguing mechanisms governing cell protrusion and the formation of actin dependent structures. For example, successive deletion of all VASP-family members – VASP, Mena and Evl – lead to virtual removal of microspikes in the lamellipodium and strongly reduced protrusion speed, but formation of lamellipodia was still possible (Damiano-Guercio et al. 2020). Interestingly however, Arp2/3 complex and CP both appeared to be more strongly localized to the lamellipodium. Earlier observations in the field had ascribed an anti-capping activity to VASP family members and thus proposed an antagonistic relationship between VASP and CP (Bear et al. 2002), the precise molecular reason for this, however, has remained unclear (Trichet et al. 2008; Faix and Rottner 2022).

In 2008, capping protein was also already described to promote Arp2/3-dependent actin assembly by favoring branching over filament elongation (Akin and Mullins 2008), however, the precise mechanism mediating this phenomenon has long remained elusive. A more recent study focusing on its structure using Cryo-EM images enabled the proposal of a comprehensive molecular mechanism, how capping of barbed ends by CP can lead to Arp2/3 complex activation by WH2 binding site masking (Funk et al. 2021). As previously described, the heterodimeric CP harbors short appendices at the C-terminal ends of both α - and β -subunit coined α and β tentacle, respectively. Both were ascribed a role in actin binding and in increasing the affinity of CP for barbed ends (Wear et al. 2003), and it became clear in the meantime that the tentacles share sequence similarities with the so called WH2-domains in NPFs mediating actin binding. Funk et al. then recently showed that removal of the β -tentacle does not have a large

impact on capping, but instead reduces Arp2/3-dependent branching by non-productively tethering the WH2-domains of NPFs to the terminal actin subunit of growing filaments. In contrast, the presence of the β -tentacle in wild-type CP frees the NPF for new rounds of Arp2/3 activation, thus potentiating Arp2/3-dependent actin assembly. Genetic removal of CP in cells then – thought to be again crucial for lamellipodium formation based on previous RNAi-experiments (Mejillano et al. 2004) – revealed strongly compromised lamellipodia with apparent defects in Arp2/3 complex-mediated cellular behavior. This phenotype could be rescued by transient expression of wildtype CP β 2, as expected, but not, strikingly, by a truncated CP-subunit variant lacking its β -tentacle (Funk et al. 2021).

Finally, on-demand manipulation of genes of interest was helpful to decipher alternate routes of signaling cascades leading to lamellipodia formation in the Rac/WASP family signaling axis. Conditional knockout of Rac1 in fibroblasts derived from mice harboring *loxP* site-flanked Rac1 alleles followed by Cre-recombinase treatment already established Rac GTPase signaling to be obligatory for lamellipodia formation (Steffen et al. 2013). The largely hematopoietic Rac2 and the mostly neuronal Rac3 were undetectable in these Rac1-KO cell lines, and equally efficient restoration of lamellipodia formation by Rac1, 2 and 3 confirmed their functional absence (Steffen et al. 2013). The same conclusion was drawn from CRISPR/Cas9-mediated removal of all mammalian rac GTPases, Rac1, 2 and 3 in B16-F1 melanoma cells (Schaks et al. 2018). Finally, removal of WRC, as for instance by CRISPR-targeting of all Sra-1 and PIR121 alleles, the subunit on WRC harboring Rac interaction surfaces, completely abolished canonical lamellipodia formation (Schaks et al. 2018).

Cryo-EM of single particle WRCs then established two interaction surfaces on Sra-1 and its isogene PIR121 (Chen et al. 2017) and they have been proposed to operate simultaneously and in synergy in WRC activation. However, Sra-1/PIR121 removal followed by reconstitution with Sra-1 variants lacking either one or both Rac-1 binding sites established significantly differential functions for these binding sites. The data revealed that the site adjacent to the WCA-binding site of WAVE (so called A site), which is released for efficient Arp2/3 binding during WRC activation, is virtually obligatory for activation (Schaks et al. 2018). In contrast, the D site (distal to WCA binding site) is relevant for the efficiency of WRC-dependent, Arp2/3 complex-mediated actin assembly, hence optimizing lamellipodial actin polymerization and

protrusion (Schaks et al., 2018). So as opposed to previous assumptions (Chen et al. 2017), the two Rac-binding surfaces on WRC have highly differential functions, although they do not operate in a completely independent and separable fashion (Ding et al. 2022). Furthermore, although Rac appears obligatory for WRC activation, the related RhoG and Cdc42 small GTPases can also interact with WRCs and thus help in driving lamellipodia formation by interacting with or maintaining WRCs at the plasma membrane following their Rac-mediated activation (Schaks et al. 2021). Finally, although Rac GTPases appear obligatory for lamellipodia formation, they can even bypass WRC in specialized conditions, and drive the formation of lamellipodia-like structures through Cdc42 and N-WASP-dependent Arp2/3 complex activation (Kage et al. 2022). The latter conclusion fits more recent observations that the WCA of WAVE within WRC is also not strictly obligatory for Arp2/3 complex-dependent lamellipodia formation (Buracco et al. 2022). For further details and open challenges concerning research on WRC functions and its regulation see Bieling and Rottner (2023).

Some of the previously stated observations were already foreshadowed in biochemical studies, but only the combination of both *in vitro* and *in vivo* work allowed deciphering these highly complex and partially redundant features of Arp2/3 complex-dependent actin networks in lamellipodia. However, these networks are not only dependent on signaling status, but are also influenced by feedback loops of actin polymerization themselves. Recently, superresolution microscopy was used to track individual WRC units anchored at the plasma membrane and accumulating in protruding lamellipodia tips (Mehidi et al. 2021). Strikingly, the authors observed lateral movements of individual protein complexes preceding their dissociation from the plasma membrane. The authors then concluded that forces exerted by pushing and retracting actin filaments may very well be suited to physically remove WRC units from the plasma membrane, tuning its turnover. This is counterintuitive though if considering that increased rates of protrusion (and hence lamellipodial actin polymerization) did coincide with increased (and not decreased) EGFP-VASP intensities at the lamellipodium tip (Rottner et al. 1999). Nevertheless, aforementioned considerations suggest that cytoskeletal drugs interfering with actin polymerization might affect actin-binding protein behavior as well. This issue is discussed in a review published in advance of this review (study XXI). Indeed, Bear et al. (2002) reported that VASP vanishes from the lamellipodial tip of Rat2 cells upon treatment with low doses of cytochalasin D. They considered this to be due to a competition of both molecules for

the barbed end of actin filaments. In stark contrast, however, Small et al. (2010) reported years later in a book chapter that local application of sufficiently high doses of cytochalasin B, *i.e.* enough to completely stop lamellipodial protrusion of an actively migrating and protruding lamellipodium formed by mouse melanoma cells, lead to an acute increase of transiently overexpressed EGFP-VASP signal at the lamellipodium tip. These observations could be fully confirmed and systematically quantified over the course of this work (see manuscript XXIV below). It is safe to assume therefore that previous research on more indirect effects of cytochalasin treatments on the various actin binding proteins in distinct, subcellular structures awaits further confirmation and detailed, complementary approaches followed by systematic analysis. The data described below shows that this can significantly impact on our understanding of the mode of action of cytochalasins at the barbed ends of growing actin filaments and of their regulators.

Aim and Scope of the Thesis

There is a pressing need for novel strategies to tackle antibiotic resistances to improve treatment options, as infectious diseases are on the verge of becoming untreatable again. A major prerequisite for successful host colonization is invasion into host tissue, which has been shown to be partially actin-dependent (Stradal and Schelhaas 2018). Cytochalasins are a large group of cytoskeletal inhibitors, which were consistently shown to affect the actin cytoskeleton of treated tissue culture cells and experimental evidence suggests that they can, in principle, affect actin binding proteins. The mechanism and nature of this observation has not been conclusively addressed. Moreover and most importantly, only two cytochalasins are frequently used in literature, while the other over 400 described compounds did so far not receive sufficient attention. If there are major or even minor differences in their principal activities, *i.e.* concerning the manipulation of actin architectures has remained largely obscure. Aside from the unsettled question whether cytochalasins could be developed into cellular invasion-inhibiting therapeutics, their recently reported biofilm inhibitory effects also deserves further inquiry. However, these hypothetical application fields are contrasted by structure-activity relationship analyses that so far lack side-by-side testing in standardized cytotoxicity assays, raising doubts concerning the reliability of

previous SAR reports. Of note, the vast majority of cytochalasans are not commercially available, requiring re-fermentation and isolation from their natural sources, *i.e.* fungi.

This thesis thus aims towards isolation and description of sources for cytochalasan production in fungal genera featuring prominent producers of cytochalasans. Since novel species are frequently reported as potent sources for novel compounds, this endeavor is combined with taxonomic surveys, using state-of-the-art polyphasic approaches to classify and confirm the systematic position of examined specimens across the Ascomycota. Finally yet importantly, this thesis aims towards examining reported inconsistencies regarding the bioactivity of cytochalasins B and D, potentially laying a fundament for their future potential biotechnological application.

Results and Discussions

Taxonomic survey of Xylariales and Diaporthales and their related potential as producers of novel secondary metabolites and cytochalasan-type natural products

Several taxonomic groups were surveyed over the course of this work for secondary metabolite production and their taxonomic status. The first study surveyed a collection of different Hypoxylaceae and Xylariaceae collected in Iran and describes their morphological, genetical and chemical characterization (I). A subset of this collection was shown to be closely related to the *Hypoxylon rubiginosum* complex – a group of *Hypoxylon* species frequently incorporating red pigments into their stroma layer (Stadler et al. 2008) – with one specimen showing aberrant morphological characters different from its closest inferred relatives, *H. rubiginosum* s. str. and *H. texense*. A subsequent screening in dual-culture of the isolated and selected strains derived of Hypoxylaceae was directed against *Hymenoscyphus fraxineus*, the causal agent of the ash-dieback. This revealed that presence of the phytopathogen was commonly associated with increased production of phomopsidin, but also other unidentifiable compounds. Specifically, *H. fuscum* responded with pronounced production of an unknown compound in co-culture with *Hym. fraxineus*. This is interesting, as the two species have never been reported from the same host (*H. fuscum* has never been isolated from *Fraxinus*). The identity of the compound remains unknown due to its scarcity in the analyzed extracts and overall low production titer.

The here found potential of *H. fuscum* to produce compounds of interest prompted a characterization of *Hypoxylon* from the same collection sharing similarities with *H. fuscum* s. lat (IX) in a subsequent study. *H. fuscum* is frequently described from *Corylus*, but was also described to inhabit different hosts, albeit showing differently sized ascospores. Ascospore size was hypothesized to be host specific, potentially indicating a species complex, but Petrini et al. (1987) recommended to postpone species delineation until molecular data becomes available. Since attempts to culture the Iranian sample growing on *Alnus* wood failed, we strived to collect fresh material in Germany and Poland from the same, but also other hosts. We then chemically, morphologically and phylogenetically characterized all specimens and isolates and uncovered that ascospores' size indeed was a good predictor of independent phylogenetic lineages occurring on distinct substrates. An epitype for *H. fuscum* s. str. growing on *Corylus* was selected to stabilize the taxonomy of the complex. We then

further studied the chemistry in more detail, which finally lead to the isolation of a novel daldinin F derivative and a novel cytochalasin, pseudofuscochalasin A, which will be discussed in more detail further below.

Other specimens surveyed in this work have been collected in Argentina and comprise members of *Phylacia*, a genus with affinities to *Daldinia* (Bitzer et al. 2008) accommodated in the Hypoxylaceae (XVII). Both genera feature conspicuous stromal secondary metabolites of the naphthalene family, however, the precise phylogenetic relationship of *Phylacia* had so far not been examined in multi-genealogies due to a lack of authentic, ascospore-derived cultures and sequences. Over the course of this study, in total three different taxa were identified by chemotaxonomic comparison of HPLC chromatograms, morphological and genetical analysis. Two collections were identified as *Phylacia globosa* and *P. surinamensis*, while the third differed from the other in stromal secondary metabolite content and their lobed stromal morphology. These specimens were hence accommodated under the newly erected taxon *Phylacia lobulata* sp. nov. The presence of naphthalene-type secondary metabolites like binaphthalene-tetrol (BNT) and daldinol were confirmed in all stromal extracts, but the remaining constituents could not be unequivocally identified. It will hence be interesting to study these compounds by isolation via semi-preparative chromatography and elucidate their structures by using nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy in the future, once larger collections of stroma derived from these fungi become available.

Other members of the Hypoxylaceae showing peculiar stromal secondary metabolite profiles featured in this work showed morphological affinities to *Hypoxylon papillatum*. This species was originally described from the Americas and was repeatedly shown to diverge phylogenetically from the remaining Hypoxylaceae, resolving in a basal lineage to all other specimens (see for example in Wendt et al. 2018). A specimen derived from a new collection in the Democratic Republic of Congo was placed in a sister clade in an inferred phylogeny featuring multilocus sequencing together with *Durotheca*, separate from the *Hypoxylon* core group. This and the presence of presumably cohaerin/minutellin type azaphilones detected in stromal extracts, commonly reported from *Jackrogersella* stromata, suggested to accommodate both species in a new genus, *Parahypoxylon* gen. nov. The new species *Parahypoxylon ruwenzoriense* sp.

nov., was erected for the newly collected specimen. Its name refers to its original collection area in the Ruwenzori Mountains (XV).

In contrast to the pigment-rich Hypoxylaceae, Xylariaceae are almost devoid of stromal compounds, although being capable producers of secondary metabolites in culture as well (Helaly et al. 2018; Becker and Stadler 2021). A subset of the previously collected specimens from Iranian Xylariales showed similarities to the xylariaceous genus *Nemania*, which prompted a study of their genetic and morphological characteristics for comparison. While preparing the phylogenetic analysis, it was found that the ITS sequence of the neotype of the generic type *N. serpens* was factually never submitted to any database, although being published in a paper almost three decades ago (Granmo et al. 1999). This led to misidentifications in the literature, which was pointed out and corrected in the corresponding published study over the course of this work (XII). The new species *Nemania hyrcana* was erected to account for a collection of specimens resolving in a well-defined clade next to *Nemania plumbea* in the presented phylogeny inferred from this study. Unlike many *Hypoxylon* species, *Nemania* has so far not been studied comprehensively for production capabilities of secondary metabolites – a knowledge gap which has to be addressed in the future.

Apart from stromal metabolite presence or absence, other phenotypic characteristics have been shown to be informative for generic distinction, useful even to distinguish genera on family rank. One example are the Hypoxylaceae, which were only genetically characterized by multilocus sequencing a few years ago. A polyphasic study involving a phylogenetic inference over a larger proportion of the Xylariaceae justified the segregation and resurrection of Hypoxylaceae from the former (Wendt et al. 2018). Concurrently, the authors emended the previous applied concept that anamorph morphology of the described species is a useful predictor of their generic affiliation. This principle had initially been adopted by Ju and Rogers (1996), who divided the geniculosporium-like “xylariaceous” and nodulisporium-like anamorph forming “hypoxylaceous” fungi into two informal groups. A similar situation presented itself when studying Argentinian Xylariaceae showing morphological affinities to *Rosellinia* over the course of this work. *Rosellinia* and allied species are known as endophytes and saprobes, but a subset of species was described to occur as plant pathogens, causing economic losses on e.g. fruit orchards, such as the morphologically similar species *Dematophora necatrix* established by Hartig 1883,

which was later synonymized with *Rosellinia*. Interestingly, it was shown previously that *Rosellinia* appearing as phytopathogens feature synnematized, geniculosporium-like anamorphs, while this feature (synnemata) appears absent in other *Rosellinia* (Petrini 2013). Over the course of this study, ascospore-derived cultures isolated from the Argentinian collection were sequenced and phylogenetically characterized (V). Indeed, specimens forming synnematized anamorphs were shown to form a distinguishable clade in a sister relationship to the remaining surveyed *Rosellinia* species. Since a fitting generic name had already been introduced by Hartig 1883, the name *Dematophora* was resurrected with the prominent phytopathogen *D. necatrix* as its type, accommodating all *Rosellinia* species reported to express synnematized, geniculolpsporium-like conidiogenous structures. A subsequent characterization of secondary metabolite productive capabilities revealed that the surveyed *Rosellinia* and closely related strains were able to produce a series of nematicidal cyclooctadepsipeptides related to the PF1022 series, which were not produced by the *Dematophora* strains. A similar observation, *i.e.* that PF1022 production is more widespread in allies of *Rosellinia* had already been shared in a patent before, but not substantiated in a scientific publication (Harder et al. 2011). It is tempting to speculate if the production of this nematicidal compounds fulfills a specific ecological role, such as protecting plants from being preyed on by nematodes. Apart from this, we here unequivocally settle the identity of the original strain patented for PF1022A production, which was isolated as an endophyte (Harder and Von Samson-Himmelstjerna 2002; Harder et al. 2011) by comparison of sequence information with the here reported ascospore-derived isolates of *Rosellinia corticium*, with which the patented strain shares significant sequence homology. Finally, yet importantly, it should be noted that a third anamorph-type was reported for *Rosellinia* of the thelena group (Petrini 2013), possibly pointing towards a third embedded genus, but lack of authentic strains for phylogenetic analysis prevents addressing this question.

This study was followed up upon during the course of this work with an extensive chemical screening of *Rosellinia* and *Dematophora* isolates in solid-state cultures derived from specimens collected from Iran published in XIII. Phylogenetic characterization revealed affinities of the isolated strains to *Rosellinia corticium* and *Dematophora necatrix*, while one specimen was somewhat dissimilar to the description of *R. akulovii* and was hence treated as *R. cf. akulovii* for the lack of further discriminatory characters and multiple representatives of this collection to compare it

with. The acquisition of additional representatives of this fungus may potentially lead to the description of a novel species in the future. Chemical screening and a subsequent isolation campaign yielded a series of known and unknown secondary metabolites, which were further characterized for their antimicrobial and cytotoxic potential. Among those, three cytochalasins were isolated, which will be discussed in more detail in a later section of this work.

Another genus of phytopathogenic fungi surveyed in this work was shown to belong to the genus *Diaporthe* (Sordariales). This genus comprises several hundred taxa that are commonly isolated from vineyards and diseased crops and lead to huge economic losses (Guarnaccia and Crous 2017; Guarnaccia et al. 2018; Wang et al. 2021). Most of the described taxa were described based on anamorph morphology, which were previously circumscribed under the name *Phomopsis*, while *Diaporthe* represented the corresponding teleomorph until both were unified in the latter under the one-fungus-one-name (1F1N) paradigm (Rossman et al. 2015). Most described taxa have never been sequenced or thoroughly genetically characterized, rendering systematic description of biodiversity very difficult, especially so since no type-derived sequence data is available for most taxa (Hilário et al. 2021). Moreover, the genus was repeatedly shown to be paraphyletic, foreshadowing a systematic revision possibly going to be facilitated by genome data to establish sound species and genus boundaries, as phenotypic characters were repeatedly shown to be highly plastic (Hilário et al. 2021). Nevertheless, *Diaporthe* spp. have been shown to be prolific producers of secondary metabolites in culture, exploitable for drug discovery campaigns (Chepkirui and Stadler 2017). A collection of African *Diaporthe* spp. was subjected to a polyphasic taxonomic characterization and subsequent chemical characterization, yielding in total six new species (*D. breyniae* sp. nov., *D. africana* sp. nov., *D. brideliae* sp. nov., *D. cameroonensis* sp. nov., *D. pseudoanacardii* sp. nov. and *D. rauvolfiae* sp. nov.) and one strain tentatively identified as *D. cf. ueckeri*, and a series of new and known secondary metabolites (XI, XIV, XVI, XX). All isolated compounds were subjected to antimicrobial and cytotoxic testing, while a subset of isolated substances corresponding to the cytochalasan family was characterized in more detail. This will be covered in a later section of this work.

Apart from specimens showing unusual phenotypic characters, taxa described to possess unusual lifestyles may conceivably act as potential sources of interesting

chemistry, which equip them for inhabiting their ecological niche. In this work, the ex-holotype strain of *Hypoxylon invadens*, a fungicolous taxon described to parasitize *Hypoxylon fragiforme* (Fournier 2014), was phylogenetically characterized and further screened for secondary metabolite production in liquid culture (VI). The exact phylogenetic position of this specimen in *Hypoxylon* could not be resolved, but showed affinities towards *Hypoxylon trugodes*, a member of the *H. rubiginosum* complex. The reason for the lack of phylogenetic resolution is probably the lack of key-taxa or data stabilizing the clades of *Hypoxylon* in its current sense, since many species sharing morphology and secondary metabolite content with *H. trugodes* had not yet been sequenced at that time. Another reason could be the presence of so called ‘rogue taxa’ – taxa that are poorly resolved in phylogenetic trees and destabilize tree topologies – that are yet to be determined (Sanderson and Shaffer 2002). Irrespectively, two known compounds were isolated from liquid culture, which had not previously been reported from Xylariales, and weak antimicrobial and cytotoxic properties was documented. Later, it could be shown that *H. invadens* is related to *H. macrocarpum* (XXIII) in a study featuring full-genome data published over the course of this work, which will be mentioned in further detail below.

H. invadens and *H. macrocarpum* had both been examined for a conspicuous odor when cultured on solid-state medium, which was later rationalized to be due to the production of volatile organic compounds (VOCs; Dickschat et al. 2018). This trait is shared by members of the xylarialean and primarily endophytic genus *Muscodor*. Over the course of this work, strains derived from a collection of specimens akin to the reported teleomorph of *Induratia apiospora* were phylogenetically analyzed (III) and shown to cluster together with taxa accommodated in *Muscodor*. This genus was historically erected to accommodate sterile endophytes, but its status was under constant debate due to a lack of describable characteristics apart from gene sequencing and low adherence to good taxonomic practices in literature (discussed in III). Hence, the newly acquired data allowed the correlation of these endophytes with a physical specimen for the first time. Moreover, the data suggested that the teleomorph of *Muscodor* is *Induratia*, prompting the linkage of both, with *Induratia* taking priority due to being described earlier. Furthermore, a new family was erected to accommodate the apiosporous Induratiaceae based on morphological and genetical traits. However, the identification of the newly collected specimen as *Induratia* was based on a comparison with picture material (iconotype) of the presumably lost

holotype of *Induratia apiospora*, and no culture was available to compare generated sequences with. Later in this work (XXII), a culture of *I. apiospora* deposited at the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) was re-discovered and determined as an ex-type strain that was apparently not mentioned in the publication featuring the original species description (Samuels et al. 1987, personal communication with the first author Gary Samuels). The strain was ordered and the anamorph morphology determined to be identical to the one originally described, hence leaving no doubt in the identity of the strain. Strikingly, subsequent multilocus sequencing and phylogenetic inference revealed that this strain actually shares affinities with members of the recently erected Barrmaeliaceae (Voglmayr et al. 2018), a sister family to the Xylariaceae. Moreover, a recent study described the placement of *Spiririma gaudefroyi* inside the Induratiaceae, indicating that distinction of Xylariaceae with Induratiaceae based on spore morphology, *i.e.* the occurrence of apiospores, cannot be justified (Voglmayr et al. 2022). Consequently, *Muscodor* was resurrected and formally retransferred to the Xylariaceae and *Induratia* transferred to the Barrmaeliaceae. This sequence of events underpins the importance of using data derived from type specimens and that taxonomic systems lacking openly available types need to be stabilized by careful selection of epitypes, and that teleomorphs of Xylariaceae show high degrees of homoplasy, probably indicating a lack of selection pressure on these structures. Since historically most taxonomic systems relied on morphological characters, vast rearrangements inside the Xylariaceae are to be expected.

Other attempts to better characterize and further stabilize the taxonomy of the Xylariales focused on charting the genetic variety found in the Hypoxylaceae using full genome data. Ultimately, full genome data allows the comprehensive evaluation of previously selected genetic markers as barcodes, such as ITS, LSU, RPB2 and TUB2 for the Hypoxylaceae. A pilot study focused on 13 selected members depicting the backbone of the family (Wendt et al. 2018). The first study focused on the ITS region (II), which was here shown to harbor intragenomic polymorphisms. A mock-phylogeny using this data published in the corresponding study exemplified that small differences may erroneously be interpreted as independent lineages, hence indicating the need for a more careful interpretation when it comes to inferring ITS-only phylogenies. This analysis was backed up with an in-depth comparison of acquired genome data of the 13-selected Hypoxylaceae, published in VIII. This analysis confirmed the previously proposed backbone of the Hypoxylaceae (Wendt et al. 2018), but also revealed an

independent lineage formed by a marine fungus segregating from *Hypomontagnella monticulosa*, coined *Hyp. spongiphila*. This strain was shown to be practically indistinguishable from the former when considering classical taxonomic analysis. However, after analyzing the predicted genes and their potential functional classes, it became clear that the strain strongly diverged on a genome level, probably allowing *Hyp. spongiphila* to thrive in its unusual marine habitat. The full genome datasets has recently been expanded to 44 taxa published in XXIII, which allowed studying previous stated notions more thoroughly. This revealed that in addition to the ITS, also the LSU occurred in multiple copies and may contain intragenomic polymorphisms, which raised the pressing question if ribosomal sequence data is useful for robust phylogenetic analysis at least for the Hypoxylaceae, if not for fungi in general (Paloi et al. 2022). A recent study focusing on this phenomenon in other fungal lineages reported similar findings (Bradshaw et al. 2023). Considering these results on a broader scale, it becomes apparent that the utilization of full genome data will be a decisive technique in stabilizing the taxonomy of complicated taxonomic groups (such as *Xylaria* or *Diaporthe* mentioned earlier above), allowing the study of evolutionary patterns and diagnostic phenotype combinations. This in turn will foster straightforward species identification and descriptions on how to access these parameters in an effective manner.

Characterization of the bioactivity of distinct cytochalasans and implications for their structure activity relationship

Cytochalasans are widely known and used as small molecule inhibitors interfering with the actin cytoskeleton. However, how distinct chemical moieties influence their bioactivity has been surprisingly incomprehensive thus far. This is owing to the fact that data using analogous methodology, allowing direct comparison of cytotoxicity or actin inhibitory effects, is scarce. This problem is discussed in detail in a literature review published in the course of this work (XXI). Major structural differences can be rationalized to occur in three sites of the core structure (excluding dimers or unusual cytochalasans, such as the amochaetoglobosins; comprehensively reviewed by Zhu et al. (2021): the incorporated amino acid substituent, the size, conformation and arrangement of the macrocycle and the oxidative status of the iso-indolone core and PKS chain incorporated into the macrocycle.

"Vanilla" cytochalasan

NRPS-mediated moiety as in

cytochalasins

6-ring as in

19,20-epoxycytochalasin C

macrocycle as in

cytochalasin B

chaetoglobosins

19,20-epoxycytochalasin N

cytochalasin D

aspochalasins

7- keto-19,20-epoxycytochalasin C

cytochalasin E

Scheme 1: A hypothetical unmodified "vanilla" cytochalasan and major hotspots of chemodiversity occurring in the NRPS-mediated amino acid derived moiety (blue), 6-ring (cyan) and PKS-mediated macrocycle (red). Cytochalasins, chaetoglobosins and aspochalasins are commonly derived from an NRPS accepting phenylalanine, tryptophan and isoleucine substrates (blue). Sections shown in cyan and red depict examples of differentially configured 6-rings and macrocycles and the compounds in which they occur, respectively.

These chemical modifications may influence the strength of bioactivity, potential additional effects apart from actin binding, and reversibility of imposed effects on the actin network following cytochalasan treatment. A study preceding this thesis and published by Kretz et al. (2019) noted that some cytochalasans were able to impose irreversible effects on the organization of the actin network of human osteosarcoma

(U-2OS) cells. This was deduced from a panel of 25 cytochalasins, from which the authors concluded that irreversibility is a) steered by size of the molecule, *i.e.* that smaller rather than larger cytochalasins tend to convey irreversible effects and b) that this effect coincides with the presence of an α - β unsaturated carbonyl mediated by a ketone at C-21. This hypothesis was tested in study IX, in which we compared cytochalasin C with the effect of its newly described deacetylated derivative, pseudofuscochalasin A (Figure 3). Indeed, the new compound showed irreversible effects on the actin cytoskeleton, while the effect of cytochalasin C was fully reversible. This result will be discussed further below.

Figure 3: Structures of pseudofuscochalasin A isolated in study IX and cytochalasin C.

The next group of cytochalasins compared consisted of the compounds cytochalasin E, Δ 6-12 cytochalasin E and cytochalasin K isolated from *Dematophora necatrix* (published in study XIII). These structures shared a common backbone and only differed in the configuration of the 6-ring (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Structures of cytochalasin E, Δ -6-12 cytochalasin E and cytochalasin K isolated and characterized in study XIII and 19,20-epoxycytochalasin C and D tested by Kretz et al. (2019).

Interestingly, cytotoxicity and actin disruptive capabilities exhibited by cytochalasin K were found to be much lower than for the others. In contrast, no such effect was observed by Kretz et al. (2019) for 19,20-epoxycytochalasin C and D (see Figure 4), *i.e.* a reduced F-actin network disrupting activity. The configuration of the methyl groups at C-5 and C-6 is hence not strictly correlated with the strength of bioactivity. Thus, a yet to-be-determined factor must be present in cytochalasin E and derivatives, but not in 19,20-epoxycytochalasin C and D that acts as a prerequisite allowing the methyl groups at C-5 and C-6 to affect bioactivity. Fascinatingly, the irreversible effect of cytochalasin K was shown to be partially reversible, further emphasizing that stereochemical differences may lead to larger differences in cytochalasin bioactivities, at least under specific circumstances.

This phenomenon was further explored in a natural product discovery campaign surveying the cytochalasin production capabilities of a recently described putative plant

pathogen of greenheart trees, *Xylaria karyophthora*. This strain has been shown to be phylogenetically related to the *Xylaria curta* group, which features prolific producers of epoxidated cytochalasins (Wang et al. 2018, 2019c; Becker and Stadler 2021). Consequently, the fungus was screened in different static and submerged culture media, yielding one new and nine additional epoxidated cytochalasins differing in the configuration of the 6-ring (XVIII), similar to the cytochalasins isolated from *Dematophora*. The previously discussed notion, *i.e.* that changes in the stereochemistry and substituents attached to the 6-ring exert massive effects on cytotoxicity, was confirmed (Figure 5). Instead of a single chemical moiety influencing bioactivity, this and the previously discussed results suggest that the configuration of the macrocycle and the 6-ring are conceptually connected. In other words, specifically sized and configured macrocycles require distinct configured 6-rings to remain active, and *vice versa*. On another note, an additional effect was described for 19,20-epoxycytochalasin N, which is the ablation of cytotoxicity against L929 cells. The precise reason for this phenomenon remains unclear, but it is tempting to hypothesize that the C-5 – C-6 epoxide prevents interference with a distinct process in L929 cells that is still affected in other cancer cell lines. Furthermore, weak to moderate anti-biofilm activities were observed against pre-formed biofilms of *Candida albicans* and biofilms formed by *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Figure 5: Structures of the active 19,20-epoxycytochalasin C and the less toxic karyochalasin A, 6-*epi*-19,20-epoxycytochalasin P, 19,20 epoxycytochalasin N and cytochalasin P₁ isolated and described from *X. karyophthora*, and published in study XVIII.

The next published study (X) dealt with secondary metabolites produced by the Dothideomycete *Sparticola triseptata*. A strain of this species was grown in static culture, and shown to produce compounds of the cytochalasan type, which were subsequently isolated to purity using semi-preparative chromatographic techniques. This yielded in total five different substances, of which three corresponded to the cytochalasans cytochalasin B, deoxaphomin B and the novel triseptatin A. Triseptatin A and deoxaphomin B share a macrocycle of in total 13 carbons and differ in the configuration of the 6-ring and by an acetyl at the hydroxyl group attached to C-20 (Figure 6). Deoxaphomin tested by Kretz et al. (2019) differs from deoxaphomin B by a methylidene group attached to C-6, while deoxaphomin B exhibits an olefin bond between C-5 and C-6. This yields a similar pair of structures for comparison, as

described above for Δ -6-12 cytochalasin E and cytochalasin K. Strikingly, Kretz et al. (2019) reported that actin network disruption of deoxaphomin was irreversible, while the effect of deoxaphomin B tested here was readily reversible by washout. This occurred independently of the unsaturated α - β carbonyl identified to mediate reversibility for the pseudofuscochalasin A – cytochalasin C pair. Hence, the trait ‘reversibility’ seems to be mediated by more than one site found in cytochalasan structures, further complicating structure activity relationships.

Figure 6: Structures of the isolated compounds triseptatine A and deoxaphomin B reported in study X and deoxaphomin tested by Kretz et al. (2019).

Both triseptatin A and deoxaphomin B share a 13-membered macrocyclic ring, which is a common feature in chaetoglobosins – tryptophan-derived cytochalasans. Over the course of this work, a new source of chaetoglobosins B and an acetylated derivative was described from a parasite of the cereal cyst nematode *Ijuhya vitellina* (IV). This species was already shown to produce chaetoglobosin A previously (Ashrafi et al. 2017), and now produced chaetoglobosin B and 19-O-acetyl chaetoglobosins B in minor amounts. The capacity of these substances to disrupt the actin network was found to be highly potent, and their effects were irreversible upon washout for one hour.

However, treated cells also showed peculiar F-actin accumulations at the cell periphery, which was not elaborated on more deeply in the manuscript (IV, albeit discernible in published images). The precise nature of this observation is so far not understood and to the best of my knowledge, unique when compared to other chaetoglobosins (unpublished data). Further exploration of this effect is limited though at present by the scarcity of the compound, and thus requires the establishment of a stable source of chaetoglobosins to further embark on studying this phenotype. Moreover, it should be noted that structural comparisons and associated bioactivities of chaetoglobosin-type cytochalasins versus cytochalasins is not trivial. There are currently no literature reports available that offer side-by-side comparisons of both compound classes with essentially identical iso-indolone cores only differing in the amino acid-derived substituent. Chaetoglobosins are often isolated from *Chaetomium* spp. and not many cytochalasin-type compounds have so far been described from this genus (Zhu et al. 2021). Conceivably, it did not appear appropriate ever, therefore, to compare these compound classes in a single study. On a side note, chaetoglobosins tend to share an unusual oxidation pattern of the macrocycle, at least when compared to other cytochalasins. However, Zhu et al. (2021) already mentioned that a specific cytochalasin, K_{Fex}, reported from *Chalara microspora*, shares many salient features with chaetoglobosins. Direct comparison of e.g. cytochalasin K_{Fex} with the commercially available 19-O-acetylchaetoglobosin A in the here utilized, standardized functional assays will allow to conceptually bridge the cytochalasins and chaetoglobosins in terms of SAR (Figure 7). However, this compound has only been reported once in aforementioned strain, which, to the best of my knowledge, was not even taxonomically characterized. Although not mentioned in the publications authored by Thomas Fex, he apparently deposited a strain termed *Chalara microspora* in the American Type Culture Collection (strain number ATCC 46898). It could be worthwhile, therefore, to order this strain, with the aim to confirm its identity and reconstitute the production of this compound in order to close this apparent knowledge gap.

Figure 7: Structures of cytochalasin K_{Fex} and 19-O-acetylchaetoglobosin A.

The last set of naturally occurring cytochalasins examined over the course of this work were produced by different *Diaporthe* species. In a first study, four cytochalasins, namely cytochalasin H, J, cytochalasin RKS-1778 and the novel phomopchalasin N were reported from *Diaporthe breyniae* sp. nov. (XI, see Figure 8). The first two were also found in *D. cf. ueckeri* in a subsequent study (XVI), and even isolated in larger quantities. Inspired from literature reports, we attempted to transform the compounds by reaction with an acid, which yielded four polycyclic cytochalasins with fused macrocyclic ring systems, of which two were reported as new. Testing these compounds for actin disruptive capabilities showed that ring fusion lead to an inactivation of the compounds, while the compounds of natural origin showed potent to moderate cytotoxicity and actin network disrupting effects. Interestingly, acetylation at the OH group of C-21 was associated with a higher potency in comparison to its deacetylated derivatives. This pattern was also observed for deacetyl 19,20-epoxycytochalasin C and 19,20-epoxycytochalasin C and D and engleromycin in study XVIII, and was noted by Kretz et al. (2019) as well (Figure 8). How well the increase of potency upon acetylation of C-21 compares to all possible cytochalasan backbones and associated oxidation patterns remains to be explored.

Figure 8: Compounds cytochalasin H, J, RKS-1778 and phomopchalasin N isolated from *D. breyniae* and two acid-treatment derived polycyclic cytochalasin J₄ and J₅ published in study XI and XVI and 19,20-epoxycytochalasin C, -D, deacetyl 19,20-epoxycytochalasin C and engleromycin compared in study XVIII.

Interactions of cytochalasin B and D with the actin regulatory machinery

While a sound understanding of the structure activity relationship of cytochalasins is an important prerequisite towards rational designing compounds devoid of, or at least with alleviated, unwanted side-effects and improved efficacy, the precise consequences of cytochalasin applications, e.g. on actin binding proteins have hitherto not been systematically studied. Cytochalasins B and D, the most widely used cytochalasins, inhibit, or at least slow the rate of actin monomer addition onto barbed filament ends (Bonder and Mooseker 1986). This mechanism was proposed decades ago based on biochemical analyses. As mentioned in the introduction of this doctoral thesis, a much deeper understanding of how actin assembly is regulated by many actin binding factors has been reached in the meantime, although many open questions remain (see Faix and Rottner 2022; Lappalainen et al. 2022; Bieling and Rottner 2023 for recent reviews summarizing different aspects of actin assembly and regulation). This provoked the question, if, or better how, cytochalasins interfere with this complicated machinery. A study completed over the course of this work (see study XXIV) sought to embark on this question by locally applying cytochalasin B and D to protruding lamellipodia of mouse melanoma cells, accompanied by monitoring the acute effects caused by these treatment using live-cell imaging. Lamellipodia are a major site of actin assembly and turnover, which is where many actin-binding factors are concentrated, thus displaying ideal targets to study immediate changes to actin network morphology and actin regulator behavior imposed by cytochalasin treatment. Distinct fluorescently-tagged proteins were transiently overexpressed, which allowed intracellular tracking of individual actin regulators in presence of either cytochalasin. Notably, it could be shown that individually tested actin binding proteins reacted in a differential fashion to the acute exposure to cytochalasin B. Specifically, an important observation comprised the robust enhancement of EGFP-VASP at the lamellipodial tip. This observation was already described by Small et al. (2010) for cytochalasin B in a book chapter, but remained controversial due to conflicting observations that had previously concluded that cytochalasin D interferes and competes with VASP for barbed end binding (Bear et al. 2002). In the study thus conducted here, it could be shown that both cytochalasins B and D can lead to increased EGFP-VASP signals at sufficiently high concentrations, which was deduced, following fluorescence recovery after photobleaching (FRAP) experiments, to be due to a blockage, or at least reduced dissociation of EGFP-VASP from actin filaments located at the lamellipodial tip. Other

actin polymerases, such as FMNL family formins previously established to operate in the efficiency of actin-dependent forward protrusion (Kage et al. 2017) displayed a more moderate, cytochalasin-induced accumulation, whereas Myosin X, an upstream regulator of VASP in lamellipodial actin bundles (Pokrant et al. 2023), did not respond to cytochalasins at all. Another actin binding protein thought to antagonize VASP-family proteins, heterodimeric capping protein, however, appeared highly cytochalasin-sensitive again, and accumulated even more dramatically upon cytochalasin B than VASP (app. 2-fold as compared to VASP). Heterodimeric capping protein has been shown to represent an important factor safeguarding efficient nucleation of actin filaments by Arp2/3 complex (Funk et al. 2021). This activity was summarized as so-called barbed end interference model by Funk et al. (2021), which essentially describes how one of the terminal appendices of the two CP subunits, the β -tentacle, is able to mask filament barbed ends for unproductive binding to NPFs, which in turn are released then for actin monomer binding and thus effective Arp2/3 complex activation. Most importantly, local cytochalasin B treatment lead to a factual delocalization of EGFP-VASP and abrupt rise of Arp2/3 complex accumulation in CRISPR/Cas9 generated CP null cells. In the opposite experiment, *i.e.* exploring CP dynamics in the absence of Ena/VASP family proteins before and after acute CB treatment, no differences in responses to CB were determined as compared to wildtype cells. Hence, cytochalasin B-induced EGFP-VASP accumulation is dependent on the physical presence of CP, but not *vice versa*. The striking Arp2/3 complex accumulation in the absence of CP, on the other hand, might suggest potential functional overlaps of cytochalasin B bioactivity with CP. The structural and molecular details underlying this mechanism remain to be investigated.

Strikingly, however, a newly generated EGFP-GST- β -tentacle construct, which was increased in affinity for the barbed end through GST-mediated dimerization (Wear et al. 2003), displayed sudden and specific association with the lamellipodial tip and sites of active actin assembly upon acute exposure to cytochalasin B. This effect was specific for cells lacking endogenous CP. This data strongly suggested that CB can modify barbed ends in a fashion that dramatically increase their affinities for the β -tentacle, leading to enrichment of the latter at the lamellipodium tip where many barbed ends reside (Small et al. 1978). More specifically, it is tempting to speculate that barbed ends might be forced into a conformation by CB that favors CP binding, which would also be consistent with the dramatic association of the latter in wildtype cells. Future

structural biology-aided analyses will need to show whether this interpretation is correct and if so, what the precise, structural mechanisms behind this phenomenon are.

On the other hand, VASP accumulates directly or indirectly at barbed ends and is perhaps tethered to them upon CB in a fashion that requires the physical presence of CP. Interestingly, transfection of CP null cells with either full-length CP, CP lacking its β -tentacle and even the newly generated β -tentacle construct restored CB-mediated EGFP-VASP accumulation at the lamellipodial tip. This suggests that it is the adoption of a specific conformational change – most likely of the barbed end – that is obligatory for VASP accumulation, and which can be triggered by CB in the presence of any CP fragment, instead of a specific CP domain that would be required for direct VASP recruitment in these conditions.

Whatever the final outcome, this study added much needed data resolving the initially described conflicts reported in literature concerning VASP responses to inhibition of actin polymerization by cytochalasins B and D. They also provided a more precise understanding of how cytochalasin B interferes with the actin polymerization machinery, clearly going beyond the current paradigm of solely stopping intracellular actin polymerization.

Speaking of inhibition of actin polymerization: finally yet importantly, we could also clearly show, again by FRAP, but in this case of EGFP-tagged β -actin, that in spite of the general assumption in the field that halting of lamellipodium protrusion would be equal to cessation of actin polymerization, actin assembly cannot be completely stopped (discussed in XXI and XXIV).

It remains to be shown if described mechanisms of action extend to other members of the cytochalasins, or in other words, are conserved throughout the compound family. Again, a large, remaining knowledge gap arises from the fact that to date, no structural information of true barbed ends bound to cytochalasins B or D are available, from which biochemical explanations of aforementioned effects could be obtained. However, such data will be instrumental for explaining how precisely cytochalasin B manipulates the actin filament barbed end, allowing simultaneous tethering of CP and VASP perhaps in a tri-molecular complex, as well as derived consequences arising from such a structural scenario. Notably, the data discussed here also established that such changes on barbed ends will only be relevant at subcellular locations harboring

CP, as CB and CD-triggered VASP accumulations could not be observed at microspike tips or focal adhesions both of which largely lack endogenous CP. This notion also reveals that the use of cytochalasins in future experimental approaches will have to consider differential effects on rapidly growing actin filament ends at distinct subcellular locations.

Semi-and mutasynthesis-enabled engineering of Pyrichalasin H enables further functionalization of cytochalasans

As pointed out earlier, cytochalasins are synthesized by a concerted action of a PKS and a NRPS and are further modified by tailoring enzymes, yielding a matured secondary metabolite (Skellam 2017). It was reported that intervention with this machinery by genetically engineering the producing strain of pyrichalasin H, *Pyricularia grisea* NI980 yielded a series of intermediates that are masked or shunted under wildtype conditions and provided valuable information for the biosynthetic strategy employed by the fungus (Hantke et al. 2019; Wang et al. 2019a, b). Markedly, the authors of Wang et al. (2019b) could show that pyrichalasin H production was dependent on a methoxylated tyrosine substrate prepared from tyrosine by the gene product of *pyiA* (Scheme 2). Furthermore, the acceptor domain of the NRPS also tolerated other *para*-substituted substrates, such as halogenated tyrosines (Wang et al. 2019b). This finding was exploited in a subsequent study during the course of this work, to generate further functionalized pyrichalasin (or cytochalasin) H derivatives. Specifically, an azido-substituted tyrosine was fed to a Δ *pyiA* mutant of *P. grisea* NI980 (VII). This yielded a 4' azidocytochalasin H, which enabled click-chemistry (Huisgen cycloaddition) with alkynes attached to different functional groups (Scheme 2). This semi-synthetic derivatization strategy was exploited to e.g. fluorescently tag the cytochalasin, or label it with biotin for potential fishing experiments in the future. In this pilot study, the newly generated derivatives were first screened for retained actin disrupting capabilities and toxicity against eukaryotic cell lines as well as antimicrobial properties. The fluorescently-coupled cytochalasins were then explored as potential dyes, possibly visualizing barbed ends throughout cytochalasin-labelled cells. Four out of the five dyes showed weak labeling patterns likely resembling unspecific binding. The fifth, Texas Red linked cytochalasin H (Scheme 2), however, showed a discernible staining pattern resembling an actin network, which shared striking similarities with

labeling of the actin cytoskeleton by fluorescently-coupled phalloidin – a basidiomycete-derived cyclopeptide described to specifically bind actin filaments (Wulf et al. 1979; Faulstich et al. 1988). If this pattern was due to this cytochalasin derivative binding along the sides of filaments, *i.e.* in a phalloidin-like fashion or if barbed ends are much more evenly distributed throughout actin filament structures in cells than expected has so far not been unequivocally answered. Irrespective of this, the respective study laid the foundation for a novel technology platform, allowing the generation of functionalized compounds that may be adapted at will to enable other applications, such as target fishing for potential novel binding factors.

Scheme 2: Incorporation of tyrosin during biosynthesis of pyrichalasin H in *Pyricularia grisea* NI980 is abrogated by deletion of *pyiA*, which can be reconstituted by complementary feeding of a methoxylated tyrosin (Wang et al. 2019b). Precursor guided mutasynthesis with a 4'-azidophenylalanin substrate resulted in a 4'-azido-substituted cytochalasin H, which was further semi-synthetically derivatized by click-chemistry affording a series of functionalized cytochalasin derivatives, such as a Texas Red-linked cytochalasin H published in study VII.

Conclusions and Outlook

Fungi are capable producers of bioactive secondary metabolites, however much is to learn about bio- and species diversity, as many fungal taxa have not yet been described or characterized with state-of-the-art methodology. Undescribed and uncharted species have repeatedly been shown to constitute untapped sources of natural products, such as cytochalasans, a large and chemically diverse group produced by a vast range of fungi throughout the Ascomycota. Several new and potential producers were characterized over the course of this thesis, leading to numerous taxonomical re-classifications, updates and new species descriptions. The isolation and screening of cytochalasans in standardized assays allowed an improved insight into the convoluted structure activity relationship of cytochalasans, but a comprehensive SAR is not yet available. This has been found to be due, in part, to the fact that not only distinct chemical functional groups influence bioactivity, but also that the general size and conformation of single molecules significantly influence bioactivity patterns exerted on eukaryotic cells. A thorough analysis and understanding is further complicated by the fact that a protein structure of the barbed end in combination with a bound cytochalasan is lacking. Novel techniques, such as Cryo-electron microscopy (Cryo-EM), may help to shed much-needed light on this issue (Carman et al. 2023; Oosterheert et al. 2024). Moreover, local application of cytochalasin B and D allowed resolving long-standing conflicts in literature concerning their exerted influence on the actin polymerase VASP, and added a novel perspective of cytochalasin B potentially manipulating the conformation of actin barbed ends directly impacting on binding stoichiometry of associated proteins. Less understood, investigated bioactivities comprised anti-biofilm properties of cytochalasans, which were here explored on preformed biofilms formed by *Candida albicans* and on biofilm formation of *Staphylococcus aureus*. The results were encouraging, but paucity of compounds prevented a systematic screening of all isolated compounds for anti-biofilm activity. It is hence of undeniable importance that a path for sustainable replenishment of tested compounds is established. This could in principle even involve the engineering of hand-tailored cytochalasans equipped with specific, functionalized chemical groups for specific purposes. Recent advancements in total mycosynthesis, *i.e.* expression of genes encoding tailoring enzymes enabling targeted manipulation of specific secondary metabolite compounds expressed in an heterologous host (Kahlert et al. 2021; Cox 2024), have paved the way towards achieving this goal.

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Appendices: publications of this dissertation

- I. Pourmoghaddham MJ, **Lambert C**, Surup F, Khodaparast SA, Krisai-Greilhuber I, Voglmayr H, Stadler M. 2020. Discovery of a new species of the *Hypoxylon rubiginosum* complex from Iran and antagonistic activities of *Hypoxylon* spp. against the Ash Dieback pathogen, *Hymenoscyphus fraxineus*, in dual culture. *Myckeys* 66:105-133. Doi: 10.3897/MYCOKEYS.66.50946.
- II. Stadler M, **Lambert C**, Wibberg D, Kalinowski J, Cox RJ, Kolařík M, Kuhnert E. 2020. Intragenomic polymorphisms in the ITS region of high-quality genomes of the Hypoxylaceae (Xylariales, Ascomycota). *Mycol Prog* 19:235-245. Doi: 10.1007/s11557-019-01552-9.
- III. Samarakoon MC, Thongbai B, Hyde KD, Brönstrup M, Beutling U, **Lambert C**, Miller AN, Liu JKJ, Promputtha I, Stadler M. 2020. Elucidation of the life cycle of the endophytic genus *Muscodor* and its transfer to *Induratia* in Induratiaceae fam. nov., based on a polyphasic taxonomic approach. *Fungal Divers* 101(1):177-210. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13225-020-00443-9>.
- IV. Moussa AY, **Lambert C**, Stradal TEB, Ashrafi S, Maier W, Stadler M, Helaly SE. 2020. New peptaibiotics and a cyclodepsipeptide from *Ijuhya vitellina*: Isolation, identification, cytotoxic and nematicidal activities. *Antibiotics*, 9(3):1-13. Doi: 10.3390/antibiotics9030132.
- V. Wittstein K, Cordsmeier A, **Lambert C**, Wendt L, Sir EB, Wurzler N, Petrini LE, Stadler M. 2020. Identification of *Rosellinia* species as producers of cyclodepsipeptide PF1022 A and resurrection of the genus *Dematophora* as inferred from polythetic taxonomy. *Stud Mycol* 96, 1-16. Doi: 10.1016/j.simyco.2020.01.001.
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- VII. Wang C, **Lambert C**, Hauser M, Deuschmann A, Zeilinger C, Rottner K, Stradal TEB, Stadler M, Skellam EJ, Cox RJ. 2020. Diversely Functionalised

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- VIII. Wibberg D, Stadler M, **Lambert C**, Bunk B, Spröer C, Rückert C, Kalinowski J, Cox RJ, Kuhnert E. 2021. High quality genome sequences of thirteen Hypoxylaceae (Ascomycota) strengthen the phylogenetic family backbone and enable the discovery of new taxa. Fungal Divers, 106(1):7-28. Doi: 10.1007/s13225-020-00447-5.
- IX. **Lambert C**, Pourmoghaddham MJ, Cedeño-Sanchez M, Surup F, Khodaparast SA, Krisai-Greilhuber I, Voglmayr H, Stradal TEB, Stadler M. 2021. Resolution of the *Hypoxylon fuscum* complex (Hypoxylaceae, Xylariales) and discovery and biological characterization of two of its prominent secondary metabolites. Journal of Fungi 7(2):131. Doi: 10.3390/jof7020131.
- X. Matio Kemuignou B, Schweizer L, **Lambert C**, Anoumedem EGM, Kouam SF, Stadler M, Marin-Felix Y. 2022. New polyketides from the liquid culture of *Diaporthe breyniae* sp. nov. (Diaporthales, Diaporthaceae). MycoKeys 90: 85–118. Doi: 10.3897/mycokeys.90.82871.
- XI. Garcia KYM, Quimque MTJ, **Lambert C**, Schmidt K, Primahana G, Stradal TEB, Ratzenböck A, Dahse HM, Phukhamsakda C, Stadler M, Surup F, Macabeo APG. 2022. Antiproliferative and Cytotoxic Cytochalasins from *Sparticola triseptata* Inhibit Actin Polymerization and Aggregation. Journal of Fungi 5(6):560. Doi: 10.3390/jof8060560.
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- XVI. Matio Kemkuignou B, **Lambert C**, Schmidt K, Schweizer L, Anoumedem EGM, Kouam SF, Stadler M, Stradal T, Marin-Felix Y. 2023. Unreported cytochalasins from an acid-mediated transformation of cytochalasin J isolated from *Diaporthe* cf. *ueckeri*. Fitoterapia 166:105434. Doi: 10.1016/j.fitote.2023.105434.
- XVII. **Lambert C**, Schiefelbein R, Jaimez JA, Stadler M, Sir EB. 2023. Studies on Argentine *Phylacia* species (Hypoxylaceae) using a polythetic taxonomic approach. Mycol Prog 22(4):27. Doi: 10.1007/s11557-023-01875-8.
- XVIII. **Lambert C**, Shao L, Zeng H, Surup F, Saetang P, Aime MC, Husbands DR, Rottner K, Stradal TEB, Stadler M. 2023. Cytochalasans produced by *Xylaria karyophthora* and their biological activities. Mycologia 115(3):277-287. Doi: 10.1080/00275514.2023.2188868.
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